

ISW

In silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of *In silico* Trials
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Policy white paper: Review of policies to lower barriers to *In silico* Trials

(In the context of ISW D5.8 Deliverable – Policy paper)

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Abstract

The application of *In silico Medicine* technologies in the lifecycle of medical product development—from discovery and design to clinical trials and regulatory assessment—has the potential to significantly improve the safety, efficacy and effectiveness of medicines and devices. However, the path to realising this potential requires overcoming numerous regulatory, policy, and workforce (re-)training challenges. This white paper will examine these challenges within the context of policy development and implementation. First, an overview of the current state of the policy and legislative landscape will be given, followed by a review of the current policies relevant to *in silico* trial technologies. We will then address the shortcomings in this state-of-the-art framework, including barriers such as the lack of a trained workforce, the absence of a clear regulatory pathway, and other barriers hindering the advancement of *in silico* trials. Finally, drawing on efforts within the silico community to overcome these challenges, we will present the main recommendations for moving forward.

1 Introduction

With most aspects of our modern world transitioning into a digital era, advanced technologies are transforming our lives in many ways: from the way we communicate with one another, to the way we work, shop, and travel, digital tools are increasingly revolutionizing life as we know it. Take, for instance, digital twins – virtual replicas of physical objects being used in sectors like manufacturing, aerospace, and the environment, with the ability to predict failures in order to improve design and testing to assure safety and reliability. The domain of healthcare is not exempt from this digital revolution, where a variety of digital health technologies (DHTs) are already widely in use.

1.1 Challenges in health and care of populations

In recent years, significant progress in human health is evidenced in Europe. While scientific breakthroughs and innovations are rapidly transforming healthcare, many patients still face barriers to accessing these advancements due to high costs or limited availability¹. As healthcare expenditures continue to rise globally and budgets shrink, Europe faces significant challenges: an ageing population with increasing care needs and an ageing workforce of healthcare professionals who are not well supported². This is contributing to increasing demand for services amidst workforce shortages and overburdened personnel. These challenges are compounded by limited healthcare budgets and the increasing prevalence of patients with chronic conditions and co-morbidities. The OECD-EU's *Health at a Glance Report 2024* emphasises the need to promote healthy longevity to address these rising strains on our healthcare systems and long-term care institutions³. The U.S. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) acknowledges similar sentiments on workforce shortages, increases in care costs, and the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases, particularly in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic⁴. These factors underscore a major shift in healthcare delivery from hospital-centric models to home-based point-of-care solutions emphasising early intervention, prevention, and personalised treatments. Taken together, these trends highlight the urgent need for further innovation to ease the strain on health care systems.

1.2 Constraints of traditional approaches to assess medical products

Traditionally, the evaluation of the safety and efficacy of new drugs or medical devices has relied on experimental methods such as lab testing (*in vitro* and *ex vivo* tests), animal experimentation, and clinical trials (*in vivo*) in humans⁵. However, several factors have prompted the integration of computational models into

1 A pharmaceutical strategy for Europe, adopted 25, November 2020 - European Commission communication - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0761>

2 OECD/European Commission (2024), *Health at a Glance: Europe 2024: State of Health in the EU Cycle*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b3704e14-en>

3 OECD/European Commission (2024), *Health at a Glance: Europe 2024: State of Health in the EU Cycle*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b3704e14-en>

4 FDA Launches Health Care at Home Initiative to Help Advance Health Equity - <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/medical-devices-news-and-events/fda-launches-health-care-home-initiative-help-advance-health-equity>

5 M. Liao and K. Cooper, "Device testing: safety and efficacy," *Translational Interventional Radiology*, pp. 69-72, Jan. 2023, doi:10.1016/B987-0-12-823026-8.00034-1.

the evidence generation paradigm^{6,7}. In particular, *in vitro* and *ex vivo* tests are time-consuming, ethical concerns arise around animal experimentation, and **traditional clinical trials are both expensive and time-intensive**^{8,9}. The high costs and prolonged time-to-market not only result in elevated selling prices but also contribute to underrepresentation and discrimination, considering factors such as gender, age, ethnicity, the rarity of conditions, and socio-economic status. Moreover, **many traditional experimental methods primarily serve to reject a hypothesis, demonstrating the lack of safety or efficacy/effectiveness of a product** while offering limited insights into how to enhance the safety and efficacy/effectiveness of such products¹⁰. In this context, a valuable alternative can be found in the emerging field of *In silico Medicine*, providing **digital approaches that allow researchers to virtually simulate multiple scenarios to predict trial outcomes** without the shortcomings of traditional testing methods.

1.3 New emerging digital health technologies

Digital health technologies, including computer modelling and simulations (CM&S) and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, present opportunities to empower various actors. Such technologies can **assist**, not replace, **healthcare providers** by providing them with tools to manage their workloads more effectively. For example, they enable timely synthesis of health-related information to triage the care pathway of patients, facilitate precise and personalised treatment options, and support telemonitoring and health consultation from the comfort of patients' homes¹¹. *In silico Medicine* can assist the transition from reactive to proactive healthcare by **personalising health management** and facilitating early disease detection, which can open up new possibilities in preventive care, thereby promoting healthy ageing. Additionally, *In silico Medicine* technologies are considered critical for optimising and de-risking **biomedical product development** (including medicines, biologics, and medical devices), possibly enhancing the regulatory evaluation processes and improving health technology assessment of medical devices and pharmaceuticals¹².

In a recent survey and multi-stakeholder debate investigating the pressing public health challenges and unmet medical needs within the European Union¹³, *in silico* trials were identified as a transformative approach to facilitate efficient and cost-effective exploration of various treatment strategies and interventions, potentially mitigating the high failure in the traditional development of medical products. Overall, nearly **half (47%) of**

⁶ Faris O, Shuren J. An FDA viewpoint on unique considerations for medical-device clinical trials. *N Engl J Med* 2017;376(14): 1350–7.

⁷ Viceconti, M, Cobelli, C., Haddad, T. et al. (2017) *In silico* assessment of biomedical products: the conundrum of rare but not so rare events in two case studies. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers. Part H: Journal of Engineering in Medicine, 231 (5). pp. 455-466.

⁸ Jean-Quartier, C., Jeanquartier, F., Jurisica, I., & Holzinger, A. (2018). *In silico* cancer research towards 3R. *BMC Cancer*, 18(1), 408–408. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-018-4302-0>

⁹ Francesco Pappalardo, Giulia Russo, Flora Musuamba Tshinanu, Marco Viceconti, *In silico* clinical trials: concepts and early adoptions, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 20, Issue 5, September 2019, Pages 1699–1708, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bby043>

¹⁰ Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

¹¹ OECD/European Commission (2024), Health at a Glance: Europe 2024: State of Health in the EU Cycle, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b3704e14-en>

¹² Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

¹³ Pistollato, Francesca et al. "What public health challenges and unmet medical needs would benefit from interdisciplinary collaboration in the EU? A survey and multi-stakeholder debate." *Frontiers in public health* vol. 12 1417684. 22 Jul. 2024, doi:10.3389/fpubh.2024.1417684

the survey participants specifically favoured *in silico* tools, AI, and machine learning as the most effective research approaches for maximizing societal impact.

Building upon years of dedicated efforts by the *In silico* Medicine community to overcome barriers to the widespread adoption of *in silico* trials, the principle investigators of this white paper have published a series of comprehensive position papers in recent years, including: 'Roadmap for *in silico* trials¹⁴ (2016)', 'Concept and early adoption of *in silico* trials¹⁵ (2018)', 'Regulatory pathway of *in silico* methods for medicinal products^{16,17} (2020)', 'Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* trials¹⁸ (2021)', 'Regulatory pathway for devices¹⁹ (2022)', and a most recent one (November 2024) titled 'Advancing *In silico* Clinical Trials for Regulatory Adoption (2024)²⁰'. Finally, a “moonshot vision” paper was published in 2024, summarising decades of achievements and outlining the path forward²¹.

1.4 Scope – *In silico* Trials

While the field of *In silico* Medicine refers to the exploitation of modelling and simulation (M&S) technologies in all aspects of health and care, **this white paper delves into the sub-domain of 'In silico Trials'**, which refers to **the use of computer modelling and simulation for assessing the safety and efficacy of various medical products**, including drugs, medical devices, and advanced therapy medicinal products²². This paper is one of the outcomes of the *In silico* World project, funded by the European Commission in the Horizon2020 research and innovation framework, to advance the uptake of *in silico* trial technologies (*cfr* Appendix 1 for more details). In response to these challenges, the international *In silico* Medicine community **Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPHI)**²³ and **Avicenna Alliance**²⁴ aim to guide policymakers through the issues the community faces. This white paper explores opportunities to collectively address these challenges and foster

¹⁴ 2016: Avicenna Alliance Roadmap: Viceconti, Marco & Henney, Adriano & Morley-Fletcher, Edwin. (2016). *in silico* Clinical Trials: How Computer Simulation will Transform the Biomedical Industry. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2756.6164>.

¹⁵ 2018: Francesco Pappalardo, Giulia Russo, Flora Musuamba Tshinanu, Marco Viceconti, *In silico* clinical trials: concepts and early adoptions, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 20, Issue 5, September 2019, Pages 1699–1708, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bby043>

¹⁶ Musuamba Tshinanu, F., Bursi, R., Manolis, E., Karlsson, K., Kulesza, A., Courcelles, E., Boissel, J. P., Lesage, R., Crozatier, C., Voisin, E. M., Rousseau, C. F., Marchal, T., Alessandrello, R., & Geris, L. (2020). Verifying and Validating Quantitative Systems Pharmacology and *In silico* Models in Drug Development: Current Needs, Gaps, and Challenges. *CPT: Pharmacometrics and Systems Pharmacology*, 9(4), 195-197. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp4.12504>

¹⁷ Musuamba FT, Skottheim, Rusten I, Lesage R, et al. Scientific and regulatory evaluation of mechanistic *in silico* drug and disease models in drug development: Building model credibility. *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol*. 2021;10:804–825. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp4.12669>

¹⁸ Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

¹⁹ Pappalardo F, Wilkinson J, Busquet F, et al. Toward A Regulatory Pathway for the Use of *in silico* Trials in the CE Marking of Medical Devices. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2022;26(11):5282-5286. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2022.3198145

²⁰ Karanasiou, Georgia et al. “Advancing *In silico* Clinical Trials for Regulatory Adoption and Innovation.” *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, vol. PP 10.1109/JBHI.2024.3486538. 8 Nov. 2024, doi:10.1109/JBHI.2024.3486538

²¹ Viceconti M, De Vos M, Mellone S, Geris L. Position paper From the digital twins in healthcare to the Virtual Human Twin: a moonshot project for digital health research. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2023 Oct 11;PP. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2023.3323688

²² Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

²³ VPH Institute - Virtual Physiological Human Institute for Integrative Biomedical Research, represent the international *In silico* Medicine scientific community worldwide - <https://www.vph-institute.org/>

²⁴ Avicenna Alliance - The Association for Predictive Medicine, is a non-profit global association of industry and renowned academia/healthcare organisations, the latter represented by the VPHI membership, that have a commercial or research interest in the development of *In silico* Medicine - <https://www.avicenna-alliance.com/>

the growth and adoption of *In silico Medicine* in order to build more inclusive, safe, accessible, and effective healthcare systems.

Social science scholars have long argued that technical innovations, like *in silico* trial technologies, do not develop in a vacuum and can therefore not be studied in isolation²⁵. Rather, they are deeply entangled with the societal, political and economic contexts in which they are developed, deployed, and used. Therefore, this white paper acknowledges that their development and assessment cannot be separated from the values, expectations, and norms of the societies they are set to serve. Reflecting this, the *In Silico World* project has prioritized close and continuous collaboration with social scientists, actively setting up a range of stakeholder engagement activities to unpack the social implications of *in silico* trial technologies in development.

This white paper first presents a brief overview of the field of *In silico Medicine*, followed by a deeper dive into the specific focus of *in silico trial solutions*. It aims to guide policymakers through current challenges the *In silico Medicine* community is facing while exploring opportunities presented by the *in silico trial solutions*. This specifically concerns the recognition of the evidence generated from *in silico* trials for use in regulatory evaluation and/or reimbursement decision-making about all health technologies (drugs, devices, non-devices). Thus, this white paper aims to address the open challenges and foster the growth and integration of *In silico Medicine* in order to build more inclusive, safe, accessible, and effective healthcare systems across Europe.

Structure of the paper: The paper starts (Section 2) by situating the importance of the *in silico* trials within the broader domain of *In silico Medicine*, whereby key definitions and nuances related to the *in silico* trials are summarised. Section 3 presents an review of the current landscape of *in silico* trial solutions, categorised into six specific themes (Innovation, economic opportunities, policy, legislation, regulatory pathways, ethical and social implications) summarised into ‘Current state’, ‘Gaps and underrepresentation’ and ‘Potential solutions’. Key observations and considerations are consolidated across all themes in Section 4 and summarised as the necessary next steps to advance *in silico* trial methodologies.

²⁵ Jasanoff, S. (Ed.). (2004). *States of Knowledge: The Co-Production of Science and the Social Order* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203413845>

2 The big picture

2.1 *In silico* Medicine in the healthcare continuum

A growing number of scholars and experts, including academic researchers, pharmaceutical products and medical device developers, regulatory agents, health technology assessors, policymakers, healthcare providers, and patients and citizens, recognise the immense potential of *In silico* Medicine. These innovative methodologies offer valuable insights into complex biological processes, significantly aiding the research, development, design, testing, and assessment of medical products (drugs, devices, and biologics)^{26,27,28,29,30,31,32}.

Despite the promise of such technological innovations in healthcare, they are still often associated with high costs, which can, in turn, limit accessibility and equity in their distribution. To unlock the full potential of these innovations, **robust policy frameworks, effective regulatory oversight, and sustainable funding models are required** to ensure that such **technologies are accessible to all patients, regardless of their socio-economic background**.

For example, the application of ***In silico* Medicine technologies in the lifecycle of medical product development**—from discovery and design to clinical trials and regulatory assessment—has the potential to significantly improve the safety, efficacy and effectiveness of medicines and devices^{33,34,35,36}. However, the path to realising this potential requires overcoming numerous regulatory, policy, and workforce (re-)training challenges.

²⁶ Viceconti, M., Henney, A and Morley-Fletcher, E. (2016) *In silico* clinical trials: how computer simulation will transform the biomedical industry. International Journal of Clinical Trials, 3 (2). pp. 37-46. ISSN 2349-3240

²⁷ Morrison TM, Pathmanathan P, Adwan M and Margerrison E (2018) Advancing Regulatory Science With Computational Modeling for Medical Devices at the FDA's Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories. Front. Med. 5:241. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2018.00241

²⁸ Musuamba FT, Skottheim, Rusten I, Lesage R, et al. Scientific and regulatory evaluation of mechanistic *in silico* drug and disease models in drug development: Building model credibility. *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol.* 2021;10:804–825. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp4.12669>

²⁹ Pappalardo F, Wilkinson J, Busquet F, et al. Toward A Regulatory Pathway for the Use of *in silico* Trials in the CE Marking of Medical Devices. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2022;26(11):5282-5286. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2022.3198145

³⁰ Musuamba Tshinanu, F., Bursi, R., Manolis, E., Karlsson, K., Kulesza, A., Courcelles, E., Boissel, J. P., Lesage, R., Crozatier, C., Voisin, E. M., Rousseau, C. F., Marchal, T., Alessandrello, R., & Geris, L. (2020). Verifying and Validating Quantitative Systems Pharmacology and *In silico* Models in Drug Development: Current Needs, Gaps, and Challenges. *CPT: Pharmacometrics and Systems Pharmacology*, 9(4), 195-197. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp4.12504>

³¹ Manolis E, Garcia-Arieta A, Lindahl A, et al. Using mechanistic models to support development of complex generic drug products: European Medicines Agency perspective. *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol.* 2023;12:556-559. doi:10.1002/psp4.12906

³² Pistollato, Francesca et al. "What public health challenges and unmet medical needs would benefit from interdisciplinary collaboration in the EU? A survey and multi-stakeholder debate." *Frontiers in public health* vol. 12 1417684. 22 Jul. 2024, doi:10.3389/fpubh.2024.1417684

³³ Avicenna Alliance Roadmap: Viceconti, Marco & Henney, Adriano & Morley-Fletcher, Edwin. (2016). *in silico* Clinical Trials: How Computer Simulation will Transform the Biomedical Industry. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2756.6164>.

³⁴ Faris O, Shuren J. An FDA viewpoint on unique considerations for medical-device clinical trials. *N Engl J Med* 2017;376(14): 1350–7.

³⁵ Francesco Pappalardo, Giulia Russo, Flora Musuamba Tshinanu, Marco Viceconti, *In silico* clinical trials: concepts and early adoptions, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 20, Issue 5, September 2019, Pages 1699–1708, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bby043>

³⁶ Passini E, Britton OJ, Lu HR, Rohrbacher J, Hermans AN, Gallacher DJ, Greig RJH, Bueno-Orovio A, Rodriguez B. Human *In silico* Drug Trials Demonstrate Higher Accuracy than Animal Models in Predicting Clinical Pro-Arrhythmic Cardiotoxicity. *Front Physiol.* 2017 Sep 12;8:668. doi: 10.3389/fphys.2017.00668. PMID: 28955244;

2.1.1 Terms and definitions

In silico, a term widely recognized in mission-critical sectors like aerospace, automotive, manufacturing, climate modelling and healthcare, involves creating **digital representations of physical objects, processes, or situations**, in order to analyse and predict their behaviour in real-world settings.

- The term “*in silico*” within healthcare context refers to the digital representation (‘model’) and experimentation (‘simulation’) of biological systems in computers. This is analogous to the physical studies that use benchtop models (“*in vitro*”) or living organisms/animals/humans (“*in vivo*”) or “*ex vivo*” methodologies conducted outside the living organism.
- The field of ***In silico Medicine*** more broadly encompasses the use of ***in silico technologies within the entire healthcare continuum***, starting with understanding the (patho-) physiology and disease mechanisms of biological systems and including all aspects of prevention, diagnosis, follow-up, prognostic assessment and treatment of patients, as well as derisking development and evaluation of biomedical products.
- The underlying ***In silico Medicine methodologies*** help create *in silico* models using computer modelling and simulation (CM&S) techniques, including Artificial intelligence. The *in silico* models replicate real-world phenomena or systems by creating **digital representations of physical objects, processes, or situations** to analyse and predict their behaviour. *In silico* models can be built based on their reliance on data and prior knowledge. Since most computational models require a combination of both, they exist on a spectrum. At one end lie **purely phenomenological or data-driven models, like AI**, which rely on the availability of high-volume, high-quality datasets. On the other hand are **knowledge-driven models, such as physics-based or mechanistic models**, primarily built on established scientific principles and expert knowledge^{37,38}.

2.1.2 Categories of In silico Medicine solutions

Historically, the branching of *In silico Medicine* solutions has evolved over time^{39,40,41}. Although few variations remain within the community, we closely follow the grouping proposed by Pappalardo et al.⁴²:

- A. ***In silico patient solutions for ‘personal health monitoring and forecasting technologies’ can empower patients and healthcare providers in their health and care journey for better rehabilitation and management of health conditions.*** Its primary users are patients, healthcare providers in partnership with patients;

³⁷ Viceconti M, Juarez MA, Curreli C, Pennisi M, Russo G, Pappalardo F. Credibility of *In silico* Trial Technologies-A Theoretical Framing. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2020;24(1):4-13. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2019.2949888

³⁸ Viceconti M, De Vos M, Mellone S, Geris L. Position paper From the digital twins in healthcare to the Virtual Human Twin: a moon-shot project for digital health research. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2023 Oct 11;PP. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2023.3323688

³⁹ 2011 position paper (http://www.vph-institute.org/upload/vphinst-position-on-fp8-greenpaper-v3_5192443874603.pdf)

⁴⁰ Francesco Pappalardo, Giulia Russo, Flora Musuamba Tshinanu, Marco Viceconti, *In silico* clinical trials: concepts and early adoptions, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 20, Issue 5, September 2019, Pages 1699–1708, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bby043>

⁴¹ Pappalardo F, Wilkinson J, Busquet F, et al. Toward A Regulatory Pathway for the Use of *in silico* Trials in the CE Marking of Medical Devices. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2022;26(11):5282-5286. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2022.3198145

⁴² Pappalardo F, Wilkinson J, Busquet F, et al. Toward A Regulatory Pathway for the Use of *in silico* Trials in the CE Marking of Medical Devices. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2022;26(11):5282-5286. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2022.3198145

- B. ***In silico clinical solutions for ‘Clinical decision support’***, where *in silico* models assist and support healthcare professionals with informing, guiding, diagnosing, predicting and making decisions about treatments. Its primary users are clinicians, patients in partnership with clinicians;
- C. ***In silico trial solutions for the design, development and assessment of biomedical products***, where computer models augment physical testing and trials. *In silico* trials simulate the potential effects and outcomes of medical products (drugs, devices, biologics) in order to evaluate their safety, efficacy and effectiveness. Unlike conventional trials that use physical experiments and observations, *in silico* trials use virtual or digital methodologies, often referred to *in silico* trials as ‘methodologies’ or ‘solutions’. Its primary users are developers, regulators and health technology assessors.

2.1.3 Regulatory actors

In this paper we focus mostly on the EU and US situation. As such the most relevant regulatory actors involved are the following:

- **Food and Drug Administration (FDA)** is a centralized federal regulatory agency in the US with nine center-level organizations, which **regulates** medical products including drugs, biologics, and devices, ensuring their **safety and effectiveness** for their intended use⁴³.
- **European Medicines Agency (EMA)** **EMA** is a decentralized agency of the European Union that is responsible for evaluating the safety and efficacy of human and veterinary drugs, across the Member States in Europe⁴⁴.
- **Notified bodies** are a number of independent accredited organizations, designated by EU Member States, to assess the conformity of certain products before being placed on the market.⁴⁵ **Passing the conformity assessment is a crucial step.**

Regulatory oversight and remit of EMA: Medical devices in Europe are regulated at the EU level through Medical Device Regulation – EU-MDR 2017/745⁴⁶, while the regulatory oversight is delegated to national entities at the Member State level. EMA's regulatory role for medical devices is rather limited to supporting residual elements of combination products. Additionally, EMA provides scientific opinions for certain high-risk medical devices through specific expert panels who **benefit from** EMA's technical and scientific support⁴⁷.

2.1.4 Regulatory pathways for In silico Medicine solutions

In silico Medicine solutions belonging to the above categorisation, can be versatile and serve a multitude of purposes by being part of one or more of these three categories. Depending on the scope and context in which

⁴³ [US FDA organisation divisions](#) responsible for drugs, devices and biologics are: the **Center for Drug Evaluation and Research** (e.g., chemical drugs and some biologics), the **Center for Devices and Radiological Health** (medical devices & radiological products), and the **Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research** (e.g., vaccines and gene therapies).

⁴⁴ Europe's EMA evaluates medicinal products and issues scientific opinions and **makes** authorization recommendations on medical products, which the European Commission approves for centralized [marketing authorization in the European Union](#).

⁴⁵ [Notified bodies](#) audit the manufacturer's quality systems and reviewing technical documentation on the safety and performance of the device. Notified bodies are governed by the National competent authorities at the member state level.

⁴⁶ EU-MDR – Medical Device Regulation - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj>

⁴⁷ Role of EMA on Medical devices - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/medical-devices>

the *In silico Medicine* technologies are used, the community considers two major pathways that require oversight from regulators, i.e. their use as a **medical device** or as a **tool** that generates evidence to support the development and evaluation of both medicinal products and medical devices (see Table 1). In addition to these pathways, Digital Health Technologies (DHT) are starting to be considered by regulators in the US and EU, where the key interest seems to revolve around embracing digital tools to capture clinical trial data, for which regulatory frameworks are yet to evolve⁴⁸.

Table 1: Potential regulatory pathway for three broad categories of *In silico Medicine* solutions: as medical device for health forecasting (category A) or decision making (category B), or as regulatory evidence generating tool (category C).

Regulatory pathway of <i>In silico Medicine</i> solutions		
Track	DEVICE pathway: Category A (Forecasts) and/or B (Decision making)	TOOL pathway: Category C (Regulatory)
Details	<i>In silico Medicine</i> solution as a DEVICE with regulatory oversight and approval (e.g. Conformity assessment certification CE) for market authorisation.	<i>In silico</i> trial solution as a regulatory testing TOOL / METHODOLOGY , with regulatory oversight, but not necessarily certified as medical device.
User	Health care professionals and/ or patients, for rendering healthcare services.	Developers, regulators and assessors, for evaluating the risk-benefit of medical product.
Scope & context	<i>In silico</i> device solution operates as medical device or non-device, with a direct or indirect intended medical purpose, supporting (clinical) decision making by healthcare professionals and/ or patients.	<i>In silico</i> trial solution functions as a standalone regulatory science tool, platform or methodology, intended to generate evidence to support development and evaluation of medical products.
Pathway	Regulatory approval leading to market authorisation of <u>devices</u> .	Regulatory Qualification as <u>tool or methodology for generating evidence</u> to support development and evaluation of <u>drugs and medical devices</u>
 EU context	Pathway: Medical device CE marking Governance: CE by Notified Bodies, with oversight from National competent authorities (NCA).	Pathway: Qualification of novel methodologies for development of medicines (ONLY) ⁴⁹ . Governance: EMA (medicines), Notified bodies (devices)

⁴⁸ [FDA's Framework for the use of digital health technologies in drug and biologics product development](https://www.fda.gov/media/166396/download?attachment) - <https://www.fda.gov/media/166396/download?attachment>

⁴⁹ Unlike the qualification process for methodologies supporting medicinal product development, *in silico* trial solutions currently lack a defined methodological qualification pathway for regulatory acceptance of *in silico* evidence in evaluating medical devices. Instead, they rely on the limited scope of technical standards, which are not always readily harmonized in Europe.

 US context	Pathway: FDA’s 510(K) submission, Pre-Market approval, De NOVO etc – for details see ref ⁵⁰ . Governance: FDA ⁵¹	Pathway: Qualification of tools for both medicines ⁵² and devices ⁵³ Governance: FDA ^{54,55}
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2.1.5 Social space of In silico trial technologies

The emergence and evolution of *in silico* trials cannot be understood through the lens of regulation and technological innovation alone. Rather, they introduce a socio-technical transformation of medicine as we know it. Not only are new tools and techniques introduced, but they further reshape the ways knowledge is produced, shuffle existing roles, alter the dynamics of decision-making, and decide who gets to participate in this ‘promised healthcare transformation’.

For this reason, this white paper positions *in silico* trial solutions in a broader social space, where multiple stakeholders, ranging from computational modelers, software developers, regulatory scientists, clinicians, to patients and members of society interact and negotiate differing expectations and values. Rather than viewing the ethical, legal, and social implications (ELSI) of *in silico* trial solutions solely as challenges or barriers to be addressed and overcome post hoc, this perspective invites us to consider the broader social space of *in silico* trial solutions. As they introduce imaginaries about the future of medicine, moving from trial-based understandings of efficacy and safety to valuing model-based predictions and simulations, recognizing the social dimensions opens the door for more reflexive and anticipatory ways of governing *in silico* trial solutions, one that not only responds to potential challenges and societal concerns, but also actively considers what kinds of futures are being built through the integration of simulation technologies in healthcare.

2.2 Current state of In silico Medicine solutions

2.2.1 Successful adoption of In silico Medical Device solutions in clinic

Adoption in clinical practice and patient benefits signifies the value proposition of *In silico Medicine* solutions for patients and healthcare systems. Table 2 showcases three successful examples of *in silico* medical devices navigating regulatory and reimbursement landscapes across various regions and making a positive impact on

⁵⁰ FDA’s The Device Development Process Pathway to Approval - <https://www.fda.gov/patients/device-development-process/step-3-pathway-approval>

⁵¹ For devices – FDA’s Center for devices and radiological Health CDRH - <https://www.fda.gov/about-fda/fda-organization/center-devices-and-radiological-health>

⁵² FDA’s – Qualification program for Drug Development Tools <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/development-approval-process-drugs/drug-development-tools-ddts>

⁵³ FDA’s – [Qualification program for Medical Device Development Tools \(MDDT\)](#) and [Catalog of Regulatory Science Tools to Help Assess New Medical Devices](#) in the absence of MDDT

⁵⁴ For Drug Development Tool program - FDA division Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER) and Center for Biologics (CBER);

⁵⁵ For Medical Device Development Tool program - Center for devices and radiological Health (CDRH) - <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/medical-device-development-tools-mddt>

patients^{56,57}. Typically, the first regulatory approval was received in Europe (CE marking) – pre-EU-MDR⁵⁸, followed by the US FDA, whereas subsequent upgrades seem to be directed further in the US. Positive reimbursement decisions were first obtained in the US and appear to have taken about a decade. Reimbursement decisions in the European Union could not be located in the public domain. A tangible demonstration of how *In silico* Medicine solutions advance treatment and could save costs for health systems is provided by the assessment by the UK HTA body. NICE estimated that by 2021/22, HeartFlow FFRCT[®] may lead to **cost-savings of £391 per patient** (2021) and will potentially be used in 40,000 patients annually, **saving the UK National Health Services (NHS) at least £9.1 million**, see details⁵⁹. Taken together, this demonstrates the successful validation of their safety, efficacy, clinical effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness.

⁵⁶ Diabeloop DBLG1 - a self-learning algorithm that automates and personalizes the treatment of Type 1 diabetes - <https://www.diabeloop.com/>

⁵⁷ HeartFlow™ (U.S.A) - HeartFlow FFRCT- Fractional Flow Reserve CT Analysis - for evaluating and managing coronary artery disease - <https://www.heartflow.com/heartflow-ffrct-analysis/>

⁵⁸ EU-MDR – Medical Device Regulation - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj>

⁵⁹ HeartFlow FFRct for the computation of fractional flow reserve from coronary CT angiography, was assessed by NICE – the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence and published its Guidance report dt. 13, February 2017 - estimates that by 2021/22, HeartFlow FFRCT[®] will be used in 40,000 patients annually, saving the NHS at least £9.1 million – Full report: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/mtg32/resources/heartflow-ffrct-for-estimating-fractional-flow-reserve-from-coronary-ct-angiography-pdf-64371991952581>

Table 2: Illustrative example of three successful *in silico* medical solutions navigating the regulatory pathway corresponding to medical devices in multiple geographies, with considerable success on positive reimbursement decisions, facilitating clinical adoption (**No public data on reimbursement in EU).

	Success stories of <i>In silico</i> Medicine solutions (clinician facing – category B)		
Company	inHeart	FEOps, a Materialise company	HeartFlow, Inc
Found	2017, Pessac	2009, Gent	2010, Mountain View, CA
Country	France	Belgium	USA
Sector	SME	SME	SME
Products	inHEART™ - 2019	TAVIguide™ - 2015 HeartGuide™ - 2019 / 2023	FFRCT Generations (2014, '18, '21); Roadmap™, HeartFlow ONE™
Organ/ Pathology	Cardiovascular- Electrophysiology interventions	Cardiovascular - Left Atrial Appendage Occlusion (LAAO)	Cardiovascular - coronary artery disease (CAD)
Description	inHEART deliver AI-enabled, digital twin of the heart to advance the care of patients living with cardiac disease. The digital twin of the heart for image guided ablations.	FEOps is a recognized pioneer in the field of physics-based simulations for minimally invasive cardiovascular devices and procedures.	HeartFlow's non-invasive HeartFlow FFRCT Analysis creates a personalized three-dimensional model of the heart. Clinicians can use this model to evaluate the impact a blockage has on blood flow and determine the best treatment for patients.
Product risk class	Software as Medical Device EU: Class IIa US: Class 1 and then class 2	Software as Medical Device EU: Class IIa US: Class 2	Software as Medical Device EU: Class IIa US: Class 2 deNovo (510k)
Regulatory approval	2019		
Positive reimbursement decision**	2018		

2.2.2 Successful use of *In silico* Trial solutions for evidence generation

In silico trial solutions (Category C in Table 1) have started to **progress towards regulatory acceptance as qualified scientific tools**. Both the EU and the US offer voluntary qualification pathways for novel drug

development tools. These pathways prioritise robust scientific evidence and validated data to support the intended use of the tool, with opportunities for early interaction and scientific guidance from regulatory agencies. Encouragingly, a few early applicants in Europe have received positive evaluations for *in silico* trial solutions through the European Medicines Agency (EMA)'s qualification procedure. While multiple reviews and reflection papers have provided a general overview of the procedure and the associated nuances^{60,61,62,63}, further examples pertaining to *in silico* trial solutions are also reported⁶⁴.

Examples

- **Europe** - EMA's Qualification program^{65,66}: Mobilise-D digital mobility outcomes as monitoring biomarkers⁶⁷, Prognostic Covariate Adjustment (PROCOVA™)⁶⁸, Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis disease model (UISS)⁶⁹;
- **United States (FDA)**: VICTRE - Virtual Clinical Trial for Regulatory Evaluation-Regulatory Science Tool^{70,71}; Virtual MRI Safety Evaluations of Medical Devices⁷²

⁶⁰ Bakker E, Hendrikse NM, Ehmann F, et al. Biomarker Qualification at the European Medicines Agency: A Review of Biomarker Qualification Procedures From 2008 to 2020. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.* 2022;112(1):69-80. doi:10.1002/cpt.2554

⁶¹ Giannuzzi V, Bertolani A, Torretta S, et al. Innovative research methodologies in the EU regulatory framework: an analysis of EMA qualification procedures from a pediatric perspective. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2024;11:1369547. Published 2024 Mar 28. doi:10.3389/fmed.2024.1369547

⁶² Viceconti M, Hernandez Penna S, Dartee W, et al. Toward a Regulatory Qualification of Real-World Mobility Performance Biomarkers in Parkinson's Patients Using Digital Mobility Outcomes. *Sensors (Basel).* 2020;20(20):5920. Published 2020 Oct 20. doi:10.3390/s20205920

⁶³ Rochester L, Mazzà C, Mueller A, et al. A Roadmap to Inform Development, Validation and Approval of Digital Mobility Outcomes: The Mobilise-D Approach. *Digit Biomark.* 2020;4(Suppl 1):13-27. Published 2020 Nov 26. doi:10.1159/000512513

⁶⁴ Extracts from exchanges with regulators, shared in the public domain – e.g. (a) Qualification advice with EMA for Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis Disease Model (ISW [QA- UISS-TB](#))

⁶⁵ EMA's Qualification program for research and development of pharmaceuticals – 'Qualification of novel methodologies for medicine development' - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development>

⁶⁶ EMA's Qualification program Guidance- Qualification of novel methodologies for drug development: guidance to applicants - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/qualification-novel-methodologies-drug-development-guidance-applicants_en.pdf

⁶⁷ EMA Letter of support for Mobilise-D digital mobility outcomes as monitoring biomarkers - 2021 - accessible via : https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/letter-support-mobilise-d-digital-mobility-outcomes-monitoring-biomarkers-follow_en.pdf

⁶⁸ EMA Qualification opinion for Prognostic Covariate Adjustment (PROCOVA™) - 2022 <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-development/scientific-advice-protocol-assistance/opinions-letters-support-qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development#prognostic-covariate-adjustment-procova-8081>

⁶⁹ EMA Letter of support for Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis disease model - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/letter-support-universal-immune-system-simulator-tuberculosis-disease-model-uiss-tb-dr_en.pdf

⁷⁰ VICTRE: *In silico* Breast Imaging Pipeline - The regulatory science tool is a set of computer models that allow for the generation of *in silico* breast radiographic images for the evaluation of digital mammography (DM) and digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) devices. Accessed via: <https://cdrh-rst.fda.gov/victre-silico-breast-imaging-pipeline>

⁷¹ Sharma D, Graff CG, Badal A, Zeng R, Sawant P, Sengupta A, Dahal E, Badano A. Technical Note: *In silico* imaging tools from the VICTRE clinical trial. *Med Phys.* 2019 Sep;46(9):3924-3928. doi: 10.1002/mp.13674. Epub 2019 Jul 17. PMID: 31228352

⁷² FDA - MDDT Summary of evidence and basis of qualification decision for Virtual MRI Safety Evaluations of Medical Devices - 2021 - <https://www.fda.gov/media/154181/download?attachment>

2.3 Challenges to the adoption of *In silico* Medicine solutions

In spite of many areas of progress and success stories mentioned above, there are major challenges to the current state of play of regulatory pathways for *In silico* Medicine solutions. The following section sketches the major drawbacks in the existing regulatory pathways for the qualification of *in silico* modelling based solutions and defines the scope of this white paper.

Despite these early successes, *in silico* solutions face **significant challenges**:

2.3.1 Underrepresentation in policy and regulatory frameworks

- **Gaps in Policy:** A lack of comprehensive regulatory and policy frameworks specifically tailored to *in silico* solutions creates uncertainty for developers and hinders broader adoption.

2.3.2 Challenges of bridging science and society:

- **Stakeholder awareness and engagement:** Limited awareness and understanding among stakeholders (e.g., healthcare providers, policymakers, and patients) about the potential of *in silico* solutions can hinder their acceptance and utilisation. In order to align the direction of *in silico* solutions with the expectations and perspectives of different stakeholders, they need to be actively included in all stages of Research & Innovation.
- **Patient Engagement but who is “the patient”?** How can we involve them without turning them into data subjects only. The increasing emphasis placed on patient engagement raises a set of epistemological questions about who 'the patient' is and what role they are ought to take on. Such reflections prompts the question of how to move beyond the current day practice of treating patients as passive data providers. Thus, shift towards making them active contributors who help shape research and innovation. This calls for thoughtful approaches to organizing engagement that genuinely include patients in decision-making processes, requiring interdisciplinary collaboration with social scientists.
- **Social implication of translating *in silico* trial solutions into clinical practice:** The regulatory approval process of medical products has traditionally been grounded in evidence-based medicine, relying exclusively on clinical trial data gathered through rigorous human and animal studies. With the emergence of *in silico* trials, there is an increasing inclusion of real-world data, which might challenge these long-standing norms. In this light, the regulatory acceptance of *in silico* trials requires more than just the adaptation of existing regulatory pathways. Rather, it invites a broader rethinking of the principles and practices underpinning regulatory science as we know it. This raises questions around uncertainty management, evidence hierarchies, and how emerging methodologies are legitimated within institutional and clinical frameworks. These shifts are not purely technical, but inherently social and epistemological, demanding thoughtful interdisciplinary collaboration.

What is “*In silico*” (vs. AI) => Elisa Elhadj, a field in-the-making. The boundaries of what constitutes ‘*in silico* medicine’ remain fluid and contested, often associated or confused with AI in healthcare. The *in silico* community must therefore take clear and deliberate steps to address its definitional ambiguities to ensure conceptual clarity and guide its development as a coherent field-in-the-making.

2.3.3 Regulatory pathways

- While the EMA's evolving qualification program^{73,74} comprehensively addresses novel drug development methodologies, improvements are still needed. Specifically, for emerging technologies *in silico* trial methodologies, EMA guidance documents emphasizes clinical validation but lacks clarity on steps towards technical validation⁷⁵. Furthermore, current qualification programs appear to focus on methodologies intending to conduct conventional full-length clinical trials^{76,77}. Participating in such programs can negatively impact *in silico* methodologies aiming to replace traditional physical experiments, requiring careful consideration of the repercussions⁷⁸.

3 Review of current state of play, gaps and potential solutions

3.1 Methodology

To address the challenges of *In silico* Trial solutions identified in the problem statement, we set out to first explore the state of play to identify and acknowledge the key areas of progress while identifying the gaps and under-representations. To realise this, we followed the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework approach⁷⁹ as outlined in our policy brief⁸⁰. The European Commission (EC) has introduced the **Responsible**

⁷³ EMA's Qualification program for research and development of pharmaceuticals – 'Qualification of novel methodologies for medicine development' - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development>

⁷⁴ EMA's Qualification program Guidance- Qualification of novel methodologies for drug development: guidance to applicants - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/qualification-novel-methodologies-drug-development-guidance-applicants_en.pdf

⁷⁵ EMA's Qualification program Guidance- Qualification of novel methodologies for drug development: guidance to applicants - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/qualification-novel-methodologies-drug-development-guidance-applicants_en.pdf

⁷⁶ Bakker E, Hendrikse NM, Ehmann F, et al. Biomarker Qualification at the European Medicines Agency: A Review of Biomarker Qualification Procedures From 2008 to 2020. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.* 2022;112(1):69-80. doi:10.1002/cpt.2554

⁷⁷ Giannuzzi V, Bertolani A, Torretta S, et al. Innovative research methodologies in the EU regulatory framework: an analysis of EMA qualification procedures from a pediatric perspective. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2024;11:1369547. Published 2024 Mar 28. doi:10.3389/fmed.2024.1369547

⁷⁸ Learnings and perspective on regulatory barriers – [Observations and recommendations from ISW](#) project

⁷⁹ de Saille, S. (2015). Innovating innovation policy: the emergence of 'Responsible Research and Innovation.' *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 2(2), 152–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2015.1045280>

⁸⁰ Geris, L., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Rangarajan, J. R., Biasin, E., Van Hoyweghen, I., & Viceconti, M. (2024). Policy brief: Accelerating the uptake of *in silico* trials in healthcare. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534366>

Research and Innovation (RRI) framework^{81,82,83,84,85}, as part of Horizon 2020^{86,87,88}, to foster more responsible innovation, which readily pertains to *In silico Medicine*⁸⁹. RRI encourages the involvement of all stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, industry, and the public, to anticipate and address the social, ethical and legal implications (ELSI) of emerging technologies and work towards a better society. The framework emphasises inclusivity, openness, and anticipation of potential issues. RRI Tools⁹⁰, funded by the European Commission, developed an online tool that offers guidance and resources to implement RRI effectively.

The methodology used to analyse the current state of play to identify gaps and potential solutions is a multi-step process that involved the entire community of practice.

- **Step 1:** The academic community continuously strives to make breakthroughs through **technical advancements within *in silico* methodologies**. In addition, they worked on broadening the *In silico* World Community of Practice (ISW-CoP) to include ethical, legal, and social science experts and regulatory science professionals. Together, they set out to explore, understand, exchange and contribute to cross-community efforts.
- **Step 2:** Rooted in the RRI framework and guided by the experts in social science and humanities, the ISW-CoP organised a series of **stakeholder engagement strategies** starting from desk review and including Delphi studies, surveys, focus groups, reflection workshops and panel discussions. In addition, ecosystem organisations like VPH Institute and Avicenna Alliance acted as boundary spanners to bring the questions, learnings and observations to governing actors, which include policymakers, regulators, health technology assessors and health system decision-makers.
- **Step 3:** While the stakeholder engagements brought enriching interactions and external insights to the *in silico* community, the partners of *In Silico* World delved deep to **curate the state of play, analyse observations, and proactively participate** in initiatives, draw first-hand perspectives on the existing pathways, their strengths, drawbacks and hurdles.

⁸¹ de Saille, S. (2015). Innovating innovation policy: the emergence of 'Responsible Research and Innovation.' *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 2(2), 152–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2015.1045280>

⁸² Stilgoe, J., R. Owen, and P. Macnaghten. 2013. "Developing a Framework for Responsible Innovation." *Research Policy* 42 (9): 1568–1580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008>.

⁸³ van Oudheusden, M. (2014). Where are the politics in responsible innovation? European governance, technology assessments, and beyond. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2014.882097>

⁸⁴ Zwart, H., Landeweerd, L., & van Rooij, A. (2014). Adapt or perish? Assessing the recent shift in the European research funding arena from 'ELSA' to 'RRI.' *Life Sciences, Society and Policy*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-014-0011-x>

⁸⁵ Felt, U. (2014). Within, Across and Beyond: Reconsidering the Role of Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe. *Science as Culture*, 23(3), 384–396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505431.2014.926146>

⁸⁶ Felt, Ulrike. (2017). Chapter – "Responsible Research and Innovation" – In *Handbook of Genomics, Health and Society*. Publisher : Routledge.

⁸⁷ News article – 'Responsible research and innovation in the EU' – published by European Science-Media Hub of European Parliament on September 8, 2021 – accessed on 28/12/2024 - <https://sciencemediahub.eu/2021/09/08/responsible-research-and-innovation-in-the-eu/>

⁸⁸ Stevienna De saille , « The emergence of 'responsible research and innovation' in european union policy », Encyclopédie d'histoire numérique de l'Europe [online], ISSN 2677-6588, published on 22/06/20 , consulted on 28/12/2024. Permalink : <https://ehne.fr/en/node/12276>

⁸⁹ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

⁹⁰ EC- FP7 Project (2014-2016) - RRI TOOLS, a project to foster Responsible Research and Innovation for society, with society. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/612393/results>

- **Step 4:** Reflections drawn from the preceding steps were translated into **high-level thematic summaries**, which are articulated into **potential next steps** and **recommendations drawn**.

While steps 1 to 3 remain a continuous ongoing effort for the *In silico Medicine* community, this white paper presents only step 4 of the exercise. It includes a short snapshot of the state of play on the use of *in silico* trial solutions for the generation of evidence for testing and assessment of medicinal products and medical devices. Unlike this white paper, the above steps are rather broad and cover the entire spectrum of *In silico Medicine*, including (but not limited to) the *in silico* medicine device solutions and *in silico* trial solutions. The details of the actual activities and their relevant outcomes are publicly documented in multiple reports, publications and deliverable documents within the [Zenodo repository, under the *In silico* World Community](#)⁹¹ and in [Appendix 1 – In silico World Project Context](#) and [Appendix 2 – Relevant ISW analysis, reports and publications](#).

While we focus on the specific sub-category of *in silico* trial solutions aimed at derisking the development and evaluation of medical products, it is natural to step into overarching themes that impact and influence the entire *In silico Medicine* field. Given that our methodology is exploratory, our observations do take note of this big picture of *In silico Medicine* while primarily limiting the report of white paper to the specific impediments for *in silico* trial solutions, with regard to **qualification of evidence generation prior to, during and after market approval of drugs and devices**.

For each of the five themes identified in this analysis and discussed below, the **current situation** with a short **summary of the key areas of progress are stated**. Subsequently, the **gaps and challenges** in those initiatives are documented. Finally, each theme concludes with an overview of possible actions in the form of **potential next steps** to address the gaps identified.

To respect the diverse background of the intended readership of this report, reports of the landscape and existing challenges are not detailed but remain rather high-level. Subject to the interest of the reader, the detailed observations can be accessed via the links provided in the footer.

3.2 Theme 1: Innovation, technology readiness and standards

3.2.1 Current state

The Rise of innovation around *In silico* Trials. Research efforts, supported by policy and funding opportunities, continue to drive the steady growth of *In silico Medicine* field, both in Europe^{92,93,94} and the US⁹⁵. A pivotal

⁹¹ INSILICO WORLD – Open access resources of the *In silico* World H2020 Project - <https://zenodo.org/communities/insilicoworld-openaccess/records> - accessed on December 15, 2024.

⁹² Viceconti, Marco, and Peter Hunter. "The Virtual Physiological Human: Ten Years After." *Annual review of biomedical engineering* vol. 18 (2016): 103-23. doi:10.1146/annurev-bioeng-110915-114742

⁹³ Viceconti M, De Vos M, Mellone S, Geris L. Position paper From the digital twins in healthcare to the Virtual Human Twin: a moon-shot project for digital health research. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2023 Oct 11;PP. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2023.3323688

⁹⁴ Karanasiou, Georgia et al. "Advancing *In silico* Clinical Trials for Regulatory Adoption and Innovation." *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, vol. PP 10.1109/JBHI.2024.3486538. 8 Nov. 2024, doi:10.1109/JBHI.2024.3486538

⁹⁵ Medical Device Innovation Consortium – Landscape Report & Industry Survey on the Use of Computational Modelling & Simulation in Medical Device Development – February 16, 2024- Accessible via: <https://mdic.org/resources/landscape-report-industry-survey-on-the-use-of-computational-modeling-simulation-in-medical-device-development/>

moment was the 2015-16 publication of the 'Avicenna Roadmap – *In silico* Clinical Trials⁹⁶, which galvanised the pathway to establish a progressive research and innovation agenda duly supported by policy and funding instruments. The Avicenna roadmap, which was built upon the foundation laid by the 'Roadmap to the Virtual Physiological Human (2007-)'⁹⁷, and the subsequent creation of the Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPHi, 2011)⁹⁸ and the inception of the Avicenna Alliance (2016)⁹⁹. The recent establishment of the *In silico* World Community of Practice (ISW-CoP, 2020) and its Slack Community, supported by Open Access resources of *In silico* World Project¹⁰⁰.

Key Progress in innovation, funding and market growth: research efforts, funding opportunities, and collaboration between different organisations have propelled the growth of *in silico* trials. The European Commission (EC) continues to support *in silico* trials with programs like Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and Digital Europe. These programs fund research in areas including:

- *In silico* trials for developing and assessing biomedical products¹⁰¹, leading to projects¹⁰²
- Accelerating the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices¹⁰³, leading to several EU-funded projects, including *In silico* World¹⁰⁴, SIMcor¹⁰⁵ and SimCardioTest¹⁰⁶, in which VPH Institute has been part of and played the ecosystem organisation role.
- Developing an ecosystem for digital twins in healthcare¹⁰⁷.
- Personalised disease prediction and management using computational models¹⁰⁸.

The innovation landscape has also fostered the development of commercial platforms for *in silico* trials. Companies like [Dassault Systèmes](#), [InSilicoTrials](#), [NovalnSilico](#) and [UnLearn.AI](#) offer solutions for drug discovery, personalised medicine, and clinical scenario simulation. These commercially available platforms

⁹⁶ Viceconti et al. Avicenna Roadmap: *in silico* clinical trials: how computer simulation will transform the biomedical industry. Research and Technological Development Roadmap, Avicenna Consortium, FP7/2013-2015/n°611819, <http://avicenna-iscst.org/roadmap/> (2016)

⁹⁷ Fenner JW, Brook B, Clapworthy G, et al. The EuroPhysiome, STEP and a roadmap for the virtual physiological human. *Philos Trans A Math Phys Eng Sci.* 2008;366(1878):2979-2999. doi:10.1098/rsta.2008.0089

⁹⁸ History of VPH Institute - <https://www.vph-institute.org/history.html>

⁹⁹ Avicenna Alliance - The Association for Predictive Medicine, is a non-profit global association of industry and renowned academia/healthcare organisations, the latter represented by the VPHi membership, that have a commercial or research interest in the development of *In silico* Medicine - <https://www.avicenna-alliance.com/>

¹⁰⁰ Open Access Resources of the *In silico* World H2020 project <https://zenodo.org/communities/insilicoworld-openaccess/about>

¹⁰¹ H2020 – 2016-17 - In-silico trials for developing and assessing biomedical products - https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_SC1-PM-16-2017

¹⁰² [STriTuVaD In silico Trial for Tuberculosis Vaccine Development](#), [INSIST IN-Silico trials for treatment of acute Ischemic STroke](#), [SILICOFCM In silico trials for drug tracing the effects of sarcomeric protein mutations leading to familial cardiomyopathy](#), [InSilc InSilc: In-silico trials for drug-eluting BVS design, development and evaluation](#)

¹⁰³ H2020 -2020 - Accelerating the uptake of computer simulations for testing medicines and medical devices - https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_SC1-DTH-06-2020

¹⁰⁴ <https://insilico.world/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.simcor-h2020.eu/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.simcardiotest.eu/wordpress/>

¹⁰⁷ DIGITAL -2021 - An ecosystem for digital twins in healthcare - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/digital-2021-deploy-01-twins-health>

¹⁰⁸ Horizon -2023 - Integrated, multi-scale computational models of patient patho-physiology ('virtual twins') for personalised disease management - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-hlth-2023-tool-05-03>

enable pharmaceutical companies, research institutions, and others to utilise this technology for various healthcare applications.

The *In silico Medicine* community has adopted a four-pronged approach to ensure regulatory acceptance of evidence generated from *in silico* trials:

1. **Regulatory engagement:** This involves proactive communication with regulators¹⁰⁹, transparently sharing successes and failures¹¹⁰, and actively engaging with policymakers¹¹¹ to understand and address regulatory perspectives.
2. **Standards development:** This focuses on integrating modelling and simulation considerations into existing standards and guidance¹¹² and co-developing new standards and/or harmonising to facilitate the regulatory understanding and recognition of *in silico* evidence¹¹³.
3. **Self-governance:** This includes establishing legal and ethical guidelines for *In silico Medicine*¹¹⁴, developing Good Simulation Practice documents^{115,116}, and creating a library of standard operating procedures for the entire *in silico* model lifecycle.
4. **Knowledge dissemination and refinement:** This involves demonstrating scientific progress through publications¹¹⁷ and conducting self-critical introspection to identify strengths, weaknesses, and potential risks¹¹⁸.

¹⁰⁹ Early dialogues and communication through (a) formal channels for early dialogue (FDA's pre-submission, EMA's qualification opinions and scientific advice), (b) Pre competitive non-consultative, regulatory advisory board reviews with regulators and notified bodies, as part of research and innovation projects.

¹¹⁰ Extracts from exchanges with regulators, shared in the public domain – e.g. (a) Qualification advice with EMA for Universal Immune System System Simulator – Tuberculosis Disease Model (ISW [QA- UISS-TB](#)) and Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography at the Hip (ISW [QA- BBCT-Hip](#)), (c) [Medical device approval experience report](#) (SIMCor project), based on US FDA pre-submission process (d) Learnings and perspective on regulatory barriers – [Observations and recommendations from ISW](#) project, [Regulatory Advisor Board reports from SIMCor project](#).

¹¹¹ Participating and engaging in public forums like panel discussions on policy and regulatory themes, to listen and interact with regulatory and policy actors.

¹¹² Proactive participation of the *In silico* Medicine community researchers in Technical Committees of the International standards (E.g. The American Society of Mechanical Engineering (ASME) Committee for codes & standards - Verification Validation and Uncertainty Quantification(VVUQ) in computational modelling of: [medical devices \(VVUQ40\)](#), of [pharmaceutical products \(VVUQ80\)](#) in UQ40, and contributing to the revision and public consultation of standards and guidance relating to modelling and simulation – Comments to FDA's Draft guidance on CM&S - [ISW Feedback](#), as well as [SIMCor Feedback](#).

¹¹³ Being instrumental in initiating and accelerating the [initiatives of VPH Institute](#) and [Avicenna Alliance](#) movement, to draft an [ISO/IEC standard on "Establishing the Credibility of Computational Modelling in the Field of Medical Devices through Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification"](#) and representing the *in silico* community of practice in the IEC Technical Committee TC 62 on Medical equipment, software and systems and ISO/TC 276/WG5 committee.

¹¹⁴ Biasin, E., Corrêa Harcus, A. M., Elhadj, E., & Viceconti, M. (2024). *In silico* World D9.3 Implementation guidance and guidelines. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11173758>

¹¹⁵ Viceconti, M., Luca, & Editors, E. (n.d.). Synthesis Lectures on Biomedical Engineering Toward Good Simulation Practice Best Practices for the Use of Computational Modelling and Simulation in the Regulatory Process of Biomedical Products.

¹¹⁶ Viceconti, M. *In silico* World Online Community of Practice and GSP Consensus. Zenodo, 23 Dec. 2024, doi:10.5281/zenodo.14548377.

¹¹⁷ See Appendix 2 – Relevant ISW analysis, reports and publications, for specific publications, reports and deliverables outlining the progress made with regard to increasing the technology readiness levels of computation models, access to validated data collections, standardization as well as progress within regulatory, ethical, legal and social aspects.

¹¹⁸ Viceconti, M. (2024). *In silico* Trials: An updated SWOT Analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011927>

3.2.2 Gaps and challenges

Despite significant progress in *in silico* trials, key challenges persist. Maintaining long-term momentum and community engagement is difficult due to funding limitations and shifting policy priorities. Advancing increasingly complex computational models requires a cohesive ecosystem for rapid development and deployment. Regulatory frameworks often lag behind technological advancements, hindering widespread adoption. Finally, the rapid pace of medical innovation creates a knowledge and skills gap within the *in silico* community, potentially impacting collaboration and effective implementation.

3.2.3 Potential next steps

While the *in silico* community is actively working towards the clinical and research uptake of computational methods, challenges remain. Building trust through high-quality data registries for model validation and establishing robust clinical support systems will be crucial for the successful integration of *in silico* trials into healthcare. Additionally, the following steps could be considered to support the innovation of *in silico* trial solutions for the next decade to evolve.

- **Strengthening ecosystem organizations:** To maintain momentum, organisations like the VPH Institute and Avicenna Alliance require increased recognition and support to play a more significant role in driving the field forward.
- **Addressing real-world needs:** Prioritizing the development of better models, robust validation frameworks, and increased engagement with stakeholders is crucial to ensure that *in silico* innovations address the real-world needs of patients and healthcare systems.
- **Building a supportive ecosystem:** To mitigate stagnation and fragmentation, the research community needs access to a flourishing ecosystem supported by essential public infrastructures, including:
 - **Access to high-quality medical data:** Addressing the need for quality data for use in modelling, as well as the challenges of data privacy and secondary data use, is crucial.
 - **Access to high-performance computing resources:** Enabling researchers to utilize complex computational models effectively.
 - **Access to a shared infrastructure:** Providing access to a repository of advanced models, data for model development, testing and validation tools, and validated data collections¹¹⁹.
- **Adapting regulations:** Policymakers should promote flexibility and agility in regulatory frameworks to accommodate rapid technological advancements.
- **Training and retraining:** To effectively translate scientific advancements into real-world applications, the *in silico* community must be supported to prioritise robust training and retraining initiatives¹²⁰.

¹¹⁹ Need for federated infrastructures, holding catalogues, repositories and sandboxes environments, to run workflows on computational models (example initiatives – [European Human Virtual Twins](#), [EDITH-CSA Ecosystem of Digital Twins in Healthcare](#), [US FDA – Catalogue of Regulatory Science Tools to help assess new medical devices](#), Considerations of US FDA Center for Research on Complex Generics - [Model Master Files Frameworks for regulatory acceptance](#)).

¹²⁰ Examples of education and training materials: ISW initiative to formulate modular curricular for [Training the *in silico* trial workforce](#), ISW deliverable on Introductory Information Packages and Lecturing Materials for [Healthcare professionals](#) and VPH Institute's [In silico Medicine INFOKIT](#) for the research community to engage with key stakeholders.

This includes academic curricula and upskilling and retraining programs for professionals working in the decision-making arena.

3.3 Theme 2: the economic opportunities of *in silico* trials

3.3.1 Current state, perceptions and challenges

In silico trial solutions currently function primarily as research tools within regulatory science, failing to reach their full potential as enablers of innovation. While there can be many factors that we could report, one specific anecdotal observation stood out. A panel of industry leaders at the FDA-MDIC Symposium¹²¹ debated the trust and adoption of *in silico* evidence across the total product life cycle of medical devices. A consensus emerged that *in silico* evidence mitigates risk for both medical product businesses and patients. Businesses stand to significantly benefit from reduced risk during early-stage ideation and development. Conversely, the consistent use of *in silico* evidence throughout the product lifecycle is expected to lead to safer products and better care, ultimately benefiting patients.

Despite the benefits for all parties, the widespread adoption of *in silico* modelling by industry remains challenging. This resistance stems from several factors, including:

- **Resistance to change:** A natural reluctance to embrace new methodologies and disrupt established practices.
- **Lack of training and awareness:** Insufficient knowledge and understanding of *in silico* methodologies among key stakeholders (e.g. leadership teams, regulatory affairs professionals), leading to biases in favour of traditional evidence sources.

This reluctance and knowledge gap is observed across various levels within the healthcare ecosystem, including not only regulators but also the leadership teams of industry players.

¹²¹ Panel Discussion: “Model Credibility Considerations for Different stages of the Total Product Life Cycle”, amongst industry representatives from Depuy Synthes (P. Afshari), Medtronic (J. Bodner), Stryker (D. Flo) and Simq GmbH (J. Hertwig), at the FDA-MDIC Symposium on Computation Modelling and Simulation – ‘Generating Regulatory *In silico* Evidence’, Maryland, April 14-16, 2024

3.3.2 The potential

In silico trial solutions hold immense potential to **sustain, accelerate, and enhance the competitiveness** of the biomedical sector^{122,123,124,125}. To tangibly demonstrate this economic potential of *in silico* trial solutions, the Public report on ISW Exploitation Results details the necessary business models for commercialising *in silico* trial solutions¹²⁶. It also includes an analysis of the current market landscape for Computational Modelling & Simulation (CM&S), identifies potential target users, defines the envisioned market, and outlines the steps required for successful exploitation. The ISW project recently produced a comprehensive SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis detailing the specific advantages and challenges of *in silico* trials, which is available for a deeper understanding¹²⁷. The **potential benefits for biomedical companies identified by the ISW SWOT analysis** can be summarised as follows:

- *In silico* trials can **lower the financial and ethical costs** of traditional *in vitro* and *in vivo* clinical trials, therefore offering new business opportunities by enabling more cost-effective exploration of treatments. This is most significant for the area of rare diseases, where small patient populations pose challenges to conventional clinical trials, making them more costly. The same applies to ethically complex trials concerning children, pregnant women, or underrepresented minorities.
- *In silico* technologies can **accelerate the time-to-market**, shortening the time required for new treatments to reach the market by at least 50%, therefore enhancing the efficiency of the innovation pipeline.
- As *in silico* trials enable repeated virtual testing of the same virtual cohort across different pathologies, they offer significant potential for **treatment retargeting**, offering new opportunities to optimise therapeutic interventions.
- The virtual cohorts used for *in silico* testing could represent diverse populations, which makes it a useful tool to help address and **mitigate biases and gaps** that are often found in traditional clinical trials. *In silico* trials, therefore, offer greater **inclusivity, representation, and generalizability** of trial outcomes.

This analysis is particularly relevant for business executives, key opinion leaders, and leadership teams involved in **regulatory affairs**, supporting their teams to integrate *in silico* trial evidence into the regulatory

¹²² Viceconti, M., Cobelli, C., Haddad, T. et al. (2017) *In silico* assessment of biomedical products: the conundrum of rare but not so rare events in two case studies. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers. Part H: Journal of Engineering in Medicine, 231 (5). pp. 455-466.

¹²³ Jean-Quartier, C., Jeanquartier, F., Jurisica, I., & Holzinger, A. (2018). *In silico* cancer research towards 3R. *BMC Cancer*, 18(1), 408–408. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-018-4302-0>

¹²⁴ Francesco Pappalardo, Giulia Russo, Flora Musuamba Tshinanu, Marco Viceconti, *In silico* clinical trials: concepts and early adoptions, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 20, Issue 5, September 2019, Pages 1699–1708, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bby043>

¹²⁵ Faris O, Shuren J. An FDA viewpoint on unique considerations for medical-device clinical trials. *N Engl J Med* 2017;376(14): 1350–7.

¹²⁶ Carbone, V., Stanculescu, D., Van Rossom, S., & Viceconti, M. (2024). *In silico* World - Exploitation Public Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14547864>

¹²⁷ Viceconti, M. (2024). *In silico* Trials: An updated SWOT Analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011927>

pathway and **business development**, identifying new business models and pathways for commercialising *in silico* solutions^{128, 129}.

3.4 Theme 3: *in silico* trials in policy and strategy documents

3.4.1 Current state

Based on our desk review¹³⁰, it is noted that the current policy landscape, the strategy documents, policies, legislations and guidelines list a number of topics which explicitly mention modelling and simulation methods for specific applications (toxicology, paediatric extrapolation, generic medicines, etc.). Although many relevant topics do not explicitly mention “*in silico*”, some do include references to computational approaches. In addition, *in silico* methodologies could fall under the scope of alternatives to animal models, be considered as non-clinical models, or be considered within the scope of analysis of real-world evidence to supplement clinical trials.

As an example, *in silico* technologies are mentioned in the pharmaceutical strategy for Europe^{131, 132, 133} published in 2020. The strategy recognises the increasing integration of medicines, medical devices, and digital health technologies and seeks to create a regulatory framework that can properly evaluate and facilitate their development. The strategy recognises that the current regulatory framework might have limitations in accommodating new models of product development and care delivery. It proposes a revision to the pharmaceutical legislation to address these limitations and leverage the potential of these advancements.

Likewise, the EMA “Regulatory Science Strategy to 2025”¹³⁴ also referred several times to computer modelling, which was further emphasised in the public consultation following this publication of the strategic document, as well as in the EMA’s mid-term report¹³⁵. Collectively, they present notable accomplishments (see below) that show their commitment to advancing the use of M&S tools in developing medicines.

¹²⁸ Medical Device Innovation Consortium – Landscape Report & Industry Survey on the Use of Computational Modeling & Simulation in Medical Device Development – February 16, 2024- Accessible via: <https://mdic.org/resources/landscape-report-industry-survey-on-the-use-of-computational-modeling-simulation-in-medical-device-development/>

¹²⁹ Frangi AF, Denison T & Lincoln, J (2023). The Economic Impact of In-silico Technology on the UK and its Lifesciences Sector. InSilicoUK Innovation Network. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7558649>

¹³⁰ Van Oudheusden, M., Lesage, R., Geris, L., Van Hoyweghen, I. (2023). Internal Survey for ISW General Assembly: A Delphi Approach. <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740390>.

¹³¹ A pharmaceutical strategy for Europe, adopted 25, November 2020 - European Commission communication - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0761>

¹³² A pharmaceutical strategy for Europe, adopted 25, November 2020 - Reader friendly version - https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/92714c9c-6880-4708-b649-287ee9e86670_en?filename=pharma-strategy_report_en.pdf

¹³³ A pharmaceutical strategy for Europe - EC information page with relevant links to ongoing legislation and directives - https://health.ec.europa.eu/medicinal-products/pharmaceutical-strategy-europe_en

¹³⁴ The European Medicines Agency published ‘EMA Regulatory Science to 2025 - Strategic reflection’ – March 31, 2020. Accessed via: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/ema-regulatory-science-2025-strategic-reflection_en.pdf

¹³⁵ EMA’s Regulatory Science Strategy to 2025 - Mid-point achievements to end 2022. Published on 22/03/2023 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/emas-regulatory-science-strategy-2025-mid-point-achievements-end-2022_en.pdf

Key areas of progress, driven by EMA's strategic vision

- Consideration of modelling and simulation applications (as reported in review documents¹³⁶)
 - Developing guidance for Pharmacokinetics/Pharmacodynamics (PK/PD) requirements for nanomedicine¹³⁷.
 - Using M&S for bioequivalence studies in complex generics.
 - Using modelling data for vaccine efficacy evaluations.
 - Encouraging the use of **novel pre-clinical models**, including *in silico* modelling, to **support the 3Rs concept** (replace, reduce, refine animal testing).
 - Tackling emerging public health threats in emergencies as well as addressing challenges posed by antimicrobial resistance.
- Establishment of the **Methodology Working Party** (MWP, see details¹³⁸), dedicated to advancing the use of modelling and simulation.
- Initiation of work on an ICH guideline (ICH M15, see details^{139,140}) outlining general principles for model-informed drug development.
- Development of **Question & Answer** documents (see details^{141,142} on specific topics, such as Modelling & Simulation, to clarify the opinion of the regulators.
- Provision of regulatory advice to researchers in academia and industry, through channels of 'scientific advice' (see for explanation¹⁴³), leading to '**Qualification opinion**' (see for explanation¹⁴⁴).

¹³⁶ EMA's Regulatory Science Strategy to 2025 - Mid-point achievements to end 2022. Published on 22/03/2023 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/emas-regulatory-science-strategy-2025-mid-point-achievements-end-2022_en.pdf

¹³⁷ Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) - Reporting of physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation - Scientific guideline - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/reporting-physiologically-based-pharmacokinetic-pbpk-modelling-simulation-scientific-guideline>

¹³⁸ The establishment of the Methodology Working Party (MWP) and associated 3 year work program, focuses on applying new methodologies, such as extrapolation and modelling and simulation, through collaborations with various stakeholders, including HTA group – draft workplan - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/work-programme/revise-consolidated-3-year-work-plan-methodology-working-party-mwp_en.pdf

¹³⁹ The development of ICH M15¹³⁹, outlining general principles for **model-informed drug development**, marks substantial progress towards international harmonisation in this area. This guideline is expected to provide a framework for using modelling and simulation in regulatory submissions, facilitating global consistency and improving the efficiency of medicines development - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/draft-ich-m15-guideline-general-principles-model-informed-drug-development-step-2b_en.pdf

¹⁴⁰ ICH M15 Draft Guideline on general principles for model informed drug development – Published Nov 24, 2024 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/draft-ich-m15-guideline-general-principles-model-informed-drug-development-step-2b_en.pdf

¹⁴¹ The EMA's efforts extend to the development of practical guidance documents, to assist stakeholders in applying modelling and simulation appropriately. Practically, this would lead to publication of Q&A documents on specific aspects of M&S. - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-and-development/scientific-guidelines/clinical-pharmacology-and-pharmacokinetics/modelling-and-simulation-questions-and-answers>

¹⁴² Modelling and simulation: questions and answers - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-and-development/scientific-guidelines/clinical-pharmacology-and-pharmacokinetics/modelling-and-simulation-questions-and-answers>

¹⁴³ **Qualification advice:** CHMP can issue "**advice on protocols and methods** that are intended to develop a novel method with the aim of moving towards qualification". When the submitted data is preliminary to obtain a qualification opinion, an advice is provided. - EMA's Qualification program for research and development of pharmaceuticals – 'Qualification of novel methodologies for medicine development' - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development>

¹⁴⁴ **Qualification opinion:** Based on the submitted data, "opinion on the **acceptability of a specific use of a method**, such as the use of a novel methodology applicable to non-clinical to clinical studies, in the context of research and development. For example, acceptability of evaluated method (e.g. *in silico* methodology or biomarker) for generation of regulatory evidence or use in life-cycle.

In addition to the above progress areas, the **European Medicines Agencies Network (EMAN) 2025 strategy**¹⁴⁵ document and the recent draft of **EMAN 2028 strategy**¹⁴⁶ calls for Regulators to provide scientific advice and apply modelling and simulation analyses on applicant data during assessment. More recently, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) has published two draft documents: a concept paper proposing a **European Platform for Regulatory Science Research**¹⁴⁷ and an updated list of **Regulatory Science Research Needs (RSRN) 2024**¹⁴⁸. The platform aims to foster collaboration between researchers and regulators to improve the development and regulation of medicines. The **“RSRN 2024”** identifies **key research areas needing attention to address gaps in regulatory science**, covering clinical trials, regulatory processes, novel technologies, and veterinary medicines. Within the RSRN 2024, modelling and simulation are indicated to be valuable for **predicting outcomes, extrapolating data, and optimising processes**, ultimately contributing to more efficient and robust regulatory decision-making. Focus on exploring the use of modelling and simulation methods for the analysis of historical data from regulatory submission, as well as the use of M&S for regulatory acceptance towards 3Rs and translational modelling for first-in-man studies, are proposed¹⁴⁹.

3.4.2 Gaps and challenges

***In silico* trial methodologies for development and evaluation of medicines are progressing but still limited.**

Overall, *in silico* modelling and *in silico* trial methodologies are viewed as promising tools with the potential to transform medicines development and evaluation. However, their full integration into the regulatory framework requires further development and the establishment of clear guidelines to ensure scientific rigour and reliability.

While EMA’s regulatory science strategy acknowledges the potential of *in silico* trials, particularly in the context of the 3Rs agenda, it does not provide a dedicated focus on the regulatory considerations on other strategic areas. Analysis of stakeholder feedback during the public consultation¹⁵⁰ reveals a strong expectation for advancing the use of *in silico* trials in patient stratification as well as designing better clinical trials. Academics and researchers, in particular, expressed enthusiasm for the potential of these trials to transform

- EMA’s Qualification program for research and development of pharmaceuticals – ‘Qualification of novel methodologies for medicine development’ - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development>

¹⁴⁵ EMA’s European Union Medicines Agencies Network **Strategy to 2025** - Protecting public health at a time of rapid change - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/european-union-medicines-agencies-network-strategy-2025-protecting-public-health-time-rapid-change_en.pdf

¹⁴⁶ EMA’s Seizing opportunities in a changing medicines landscape: The European medicines agencies network **strategy 2028 (draft)** - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/seizing-opportunities-changing-medicines-landscape-european-medicines-agencies-network-strategy-2028-draft_en.pdf

¹⁴⁷ EMA releases Draft concept paper on the European Platform for Regulatory Science Research - open for public consultation 15/11/2024 - 18/12/2024 - accessed via https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/draft-concept-paper-european-platform-regulatory-science-research_en.pdf

¹⁴⁸ EMA releases Draft Regulatory Science Research Needs -2024 update - open for public consultation 13/11/2024 - 18/12/2024 - accessed via https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/draft-regulatory-science-research-needs-2024-update_en.pdf

¹⁴⁹ EMA releases Draft Regulatory Science Research Needs -2024 update - open for public consultation 13/11/2024 - 18/12/2024 - accessed via https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/draft-regulatory-science-research-needs-2024-update_en.pdf

¹⁵⁰ Analysis and summaries of public consultation results: EMA Regulatory Science to 2025 - Strategic reflection – published on 31/03/2020 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/comments/analysis-and-summaries-public-consultation-results-ema-regulatory-science-2025-strategic-reflection_en.pdf

drug development, particularly for studying special populations and rare diseases, and not limiting the scope to reducing reliance on animal testing. The “Mid-point achievements to end 2022” report¹⁵¹ was less ambitious in its wording than the original strategy document (2020) when discussing *in silico* technologies.

A similar trend could be noted when analysing the European Medicines Agencies Network (EMAN) 2025 strategy¹⁵² and the more recent 2028¹⁵³ update. While the 2025 strategy document explicitly sees modelling and simulation as important tools for data analysis, the 2028 strategy document focuses on the broader use of AI, which may encompass modelling and simulation as part of its applications. The increased focus on AI in the 2028 strategy is likely due to the rapid advancements in AI technology since the publication of the 2025 strategy. Overall, AI is now seen as a more powerful and versatile tool for data analysis, with the potential to revolutionise the way medicines are developed and regulated. While this is a progressive evolution, *in silico* methodologies that were explicitly addressed in policies in the last decade are now **increasingly subsumed under broader research and regulatory frameworks, often without explicit mention** (*cf.* Reflection paper on AI in the lifecycle of medicines¹⁵⁴). Furthermore, a significant issue is the tendency to erroneously categorise all *In silico Medicine* methodologies under artificial intelligence and machine learning, despite the fact that AI is just one (powerful) subset of these broader modelling approaches¹⁵⁵.

The lack of specific guidance and limited evidence of concrete progress in the mid-term review likely signifies that *in silico* modelling and *in silico* trials are currently underrepresented in the EMA's practical implementation of its regulatory science strategy.

Huge disparities exist between the policies on medicinal products vs medical devices. While *in silico* trials are underutilised in the development and evaluation of medicinal products, there is a longstanding acknowledgement and a willingness to employ modelling and simulation methodologies within the regulatory science framework for drug development. Conversely, the utilisation of *in silico* trials within Europe's medical device sector is nearly absent.

¹⁵¹ EMA's Regulatory Science Strategy to 2025 - Mid-point achievements to end 2022. Published on 22/03/2023 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/emas-regulatory-science-strategy-2025-mid-point-achievements-end-2022_en.pdf

¹⁵² EMA's European Union Medicines Agencies Network Strategy to 2025 - Protecting public health at a time of rapid change - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/european-union-medicines-agencies-network-strategy-2025-protecting-public-health-time-rapid-change_en.pdf

¹⁵³ EMA's Seizing opportunities in a changing medicines landscape: The European medicines agencies network strategy 2028 (draft) - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/seizing-opportunities-changing-medicines-landscape-european-medicines-agencies-network-strategy-2028-draft_en.pdf

¹⁵⁴ EMA's Reflection paper on the use of artificial intelligence in the lifecycle of medicines - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/use-artificial-intelligence-ai-medicinal-product-lifecycle>

¹⁵⁵ Geris Liesbet, Rousseau Cécile F., Noailly Jerome, et al., (2022). WHITE PAPER: the role of Artificial Intelligence within *In silico Medicine*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8064147>

A closer look into this phenomenon reveals that this disparity is not just for *in silico* trial methodologies. Europe seems lacking a unified visionary strategy for medical devices for a long time^{156,157}. For instance, there is no medical device equivalent to the 'EU Pharmaceutical Strategy 2020'. In addition, Europe's regulatory science strategy proposals are predominantly driven by the regulatory science needs pertaining to the development and evaluation of medicines. A similar trend is evident in the upcoming implementation of the recent Health Technology Assessment (HTA) regulation¹⁵⁸, where clear milestones and a timeline (2025-2030) exist for covering all new medicines (five years)¹⁵⁹. Conversely, the initial scope for medical devices is limited to specific high-risk classes. This is despite a Europe-wide demand for HTA assessment pathways for software utilising predictive algorithms, such as *in silico* device solutions, including AI^{160,161}.

These observations are nothing new and rather a well-known phenomenon, driven by the longstanding tradition and the **fragmented institutionalisation of the two complementary sectors of the healthcare spectrum**. While the underlying reasons and historical nature of these factors are beyond the scope of this report, it is expected that *In silico Medicine* technologies perceived broadly as medical devices or software solutions, eventually get hampered by the pre-existing trends in the medical devices sector. Intriguingly, *In silico Medicine* solutions are cross-sectoral and remain relevant for both pharmaceutical and device development, validation and assessment. With the increasing trend of digitalisation, the role and value of digital methodologies in medicine development are becoming evident for policymakers in the pharmaceutical sectors. On the contrary, the evidence for the evaluation of medical devices continues to remain limited to traditional physical measurements. Although the EU-MDR regulations do not restrict the use of digital evidence, the medical device pathways have not been paved via visionary strategies and policy statements like those of the EU pharmaceutical sector.

3.4.3 **Potential next steps**

- The policy should promote and scale the **presence and critical role of experts within modelling and simulation**.
- Policies recognised in the European medicines agencies network strategy from EMA and Heads of Medicines Agencies of member states (HMA)), should facilitate the **training / re-training of regulatory professionals** to understand and evaluate the *in silico* evidence trail.

¹⁵⁶ Fraser AG, Daubert JC, Van de Werf F, et al. Clinical evaluation of cardiovascular devices: principles, problems, and proposals for European regulatory reform. Report of a policy conference of the European Society of Cardiology. *Eur Heart J*. 2011;32(13):1673-1686. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehr171

¹⁵⁷ 'European Union: from the land of rights to the land of rules', a key figure in the *in silico* domain, Prof. Marco Viceconti underscores this growing need for more policy coherence and adaptability - see <http://secret-viceconti.blogspot.com/technologies>, specifically *In silico Medicine*

¹⁵⁸ Implementation of the Health Technology Assessment Regulation (HTAR) - [Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2282 on health technology assessment](#)

¹⁵⁹ Factsheet on implementation of HTAR, indicating timelines and milestones- https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/factsheet-implementing-eu-health-technology-assessment-regulation_en

¹⁶⁰ Elvidge J, Hawksworth C, Avşar TS, et al. Consolidated Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards for Interventions That Use Artificial Intelligence (CHEERS-AI). *Value Health*. 2024;27(9):1196-1205. doi:10.1016/j.jval.2024.05.006

¹⁶¹ Di Bidino, R., Daugbjerg, S., Papavero, S. C., Haraldsen, I. H., Cicchetti, A., & Sacchini, D. (2024). Health technology assessment framework for artificial intelligence-based technologies. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 40(1), e61. doi:10.1017/S0266462324000308

- For medical devices the long-evident lack of vision and strategy for medical devices needs to be first acknowledged.
- In light of fast-emerging new digital technologies like computer modelling and simulation methodologies, including AI technologies, it is high time an **independent centralised authority** is created **to mandate the policy and regulatory science strategies and priorities for all medical devices**, including digital health technologies. Currently, EMA is driving the vision, strategy and roadmap, along with supporting policies for drugs that embrace novel technologies to foster better drug development and assessment. It is imperative that a similar institution that fosters the strategy and policy directives, across the whole of medical device sectors is established. Although EMA is filling the role in a limited capacity, the fast pace of digital evolution is rapidly out-weighting its capacity to do so.

3.5 Theme 4: *in silico* trials in legislation and regulations

3.5.1 Current state

In two publicly available deliverables of the ISW project^{162,163}, a legal and ethical inventory was presented, providing an overview of the core pieces of legislation and ethical principles relevant to the *In silico* World project and, thus, *in silico* trials. The first analysis identified the core pieces of relevant legislation, which were analysed in depth in a second report. The key pieces of legislation discussed are the following.

- **Privacy and data protection:** In *in silico* trials, the processing of personal data, notably of patients, necessitates compliance with EU privacy and data protection laws. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) forms the core regulatory framework, complemented by initiatives from the Council of Europe and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- **Data governance in healthcare:** Data sharing, crucial in healthcare and *in silico* trials, is evolving under the EU's data governance framework. Key legislations include the Open Data Directive, Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation, and the Data Governance Act. Anticipated legislation, the Data Act and European Health Data Space are set to revolutionise healthcare data sharing.
- **Clinical trials legislation:** Addressing a pivotal barrier in the *In silico* World project, clarity in regulatory pathways EU clinical trials legislation is essential. Pertinent regulations encompass the Declaration of Helsinki, the Declaration of Taipei, as well as the Clinical Trials Directive and the Good Clinical Practice Directive, replaced by the Clinical Trials Regulation on 31.01.2022.
- **Regulation of medical devices and medicinal products:** In the realm of *in silico* trials covering medical devices and medicinal products, the regulatory focus includes the Medical Device Regulation, *In vitro* Medical Device Regulation, and guidelines from the Medical Device Coordination Group. For medicinal products, regulations encompass the Community Code for Medicinal Products, Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Product Regulation, and the Health Technology Assessment Regulation.

¹⁶² Biasin, Elisabetta. 'In silico World D9.1 Legal and Ethical Inventory'. Zenodo, 30 June 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7104079>.

¹⁶³ Biasin, Elisabetta. 'In silico World D9.2 In-depth Analysis of Legal and Ethical Requirements'. Zenodo, 30 April 2023.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991233>.

- **Artificial Intelligence:** AI, integral to *in silico* trials, is under increasing EU regulatory scrutiny. Following the White Paper and Guidelines on Trustworthy AI, the evolving framework centres on the Artificial Intelligence Act. After its formal approval, it will directly apply to all EU Member States, impacting healthcare, including medical devices and *in silico* trials.

3.5.2 Gaps and challenges

The European medical device industry, dominated by small-medium enterprises, of which *In silico Medicine* technology developers are also part, is unduly impacted by the regulatory transitions (increased cost, delayed approval, unpredictable timelines, etc.), leading to making the European market rapidly lose its attractiveness for medical device companies^{164,165}. This is of concern for the *In silico Medicine* community not only in the context of the economic sustainability of the SMEs in the modelling and simulation sector but also for potentially delaying and denying access to the benefits of *in silico* solutions to the European population.

With the EU-MDR¹⁶⁶, the use of digital evidence is restricted to provide evidence for the non-clinical stage of the process. *In silico* Medicine community at large is working together to formulate tangible proposals to include the proper use of *in silico* technologies in all stages of the medical device lifecycle in the context of the ongoing EU parliament debate (October 2024)¹⁶⁷ and newly opened public consultation¹⁶⁸ on revising the medical device regulations (December 2024)¹⁶⁸.

3.5.3 Potential next steps

As highlighted in the ISW project Policy brief¹⁶⁹, the **legal challenges envisioned in the *in silico* trials framework need to be streamlined**. The legislation on medical devices and medicinal products mirrors the issues encountered in the regulatory framework. Medical device legislation does not facilitate nor establish ad hoc references for *in silico* trials of medical devices, and therefore there is a clear need for harmonized technical standards. It is important that these standards are acknowledged by legislative bodies so that they can be used as a support for CE Marking and demonstrating compliance with EU legislation. In addition, the EU's privacy and data protection legal framework has entailed a scattered environment for health data sharing for research. Forthcoming legislation on Data Governance (including the European Health Data Space Regulation) will also have to deal with this problem. Policymakers should collaborate with users to propose

¹⁶⁴ Svempe L. Exploring Impediments Imposed by the Medical Device Regulation EU 2017/745 on Software as a Medical Device. *JMIR Med Inform.* 2024;12:e58080. Published 2024 Sep 5. doi:10.2196/58080

¹⁶⁵ Kearney B, McDermott O. The Challenges for Manufacturers of the Increased Clinical Evaluation in the European Medical Device Regulations: A Quantitative Study. *Ther Innov Regul Sci.* 2023;57(4):783-796. doi:10.1007/s43441-023-00527-z

¹⁶⁶ EU-MDR – Medical Device Regulation - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj>

¹⁶⁷ European Parliament resolution of 23 October 2024 on the urgent need to revise the Medical Devices Regulation – Debate https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-10-2024-0028_EN.html

¹⁶⁸ Commission launches a public consultation and a call for evidence for EU Medical Devices evaluation – Press Release December 12, 2024 - <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/sante/items/861619/>. The consultation and call for evidence will be open until 21 March 2025 and are accessible [here](#).

¹⁶⁹ Geris, L., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Rangarajan, J. R., Biasin, E., Van Hoyweghen, I., & Viceconti, M. (2024). Policy brief: Accelerating the uptake of *in silico* trials in healthcare. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534366>

concrete solutions in respect of the GDPR while possibly recognising the data sharing needs of the scientific research community.

Revisit previously identified gaps and recommendations: given that the full implementation of EU-MDR is yet to emerge, many of the arguments during the previous public consultations on the impact assessment report of 2013¹⁷⁰, are worth revisiting, to identify gaps and learnings for the ongoing consultation on the revision. Especially, the long-standing calls from the academic and clinical community for centralized authority for uniform control of notified bodies¹⁷¹, are relevant even today, as they closely relate to the current needs and perspective of the broader medical device sector, to which the *In silico Medicine* community is a constituent¹⁷².

Recognise the role of the scientific community in advancing regulatory science: extending Nüssler et al.¹⁷³ perspective, which highlights the impact of the EU-MDR on hospitals and patients, it is crucial to recognise that the academic *In silico* Medicine community, as a foundational contributor to healthcare innovation, is also significantly impacted by the inclusion or exclusion of *in silico* medicine considerations within legislation. To effectively address the regulatory science needs of emerging technologies, favourable consideration should be given to including computer modelling and simulation experts in medical device implementation forums such as the Medical Device Coordination Group.

3.6 Theme 5: regulatory pathways for *in silico* trials - qualification and guidance

Qualification pathways: Recognizing the unique position of regulatory science methodologies, regulators have long-established **programs and qualification pathways** for novel methodologies and tools. A primary objective of these initiatives is to build confidence in the evidence generated by these novel approaches, ultimately streamlining the regulatory submission process. This can help streamline the actual regulatory submissions, facilitate early dialogue with developers and decision-makers, minimise or help to timely identify the downstream evidence gaps, and bring overall predictability to the regulatory process. Collectively, they bring efficiency gains across the lifecycle and, in turn, cost savings, which has the potential to bring innovative medical products faster to the patients, without compromising the safety, risk and effectiveness.

The qualification of *in silico* methodologies as regulatory science tools has had an initial boost in the US, while it is still to emerge in Europe. Evidently, the trends of progression favour the US landscape, owing to the

¹⁷⁰ European Union (2012), Executive Summary of the Impact Assessment on the Revision of, the Regulatory Framework for Medical Devices. SWD(2012) 274 Final. Brussels. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=SWD:2012:0273:FIN>

¹⁷¹ Fraser AG, Daubert JC, Van de Werf F, et al. Clinical evaluation of cardiovascular devices: principles, problems, and proposals for European regulatory reform. Report of a policy conference of the European Society of Cardiology. *Eur Heart J.* 2011;32(13):1673-1686. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehr171

¹⁷² 'European Union: from the land of rights to the land of rules', a key figure in the *in silico* domain, Prof. Marco Viceconti underscores this growing need for more policy coherence and adaptability - see <http://secret-viceconti.blogspot.com/technologies>, specifically *In silico Medicine*

¹⁷³ Nüssler A. The new European Medical Device Regulation: Friend or foe for hospitals and patients?. *Injury.* 2023;54 Suppl 5:110907. doi:10.1016/j.injury.2023.110907

dedicated qualification program for methodologies that support the development and evaluation of devices¹⁷⁴ and drugs¹⁷⁵, while Europe limits this pathway only to novel methodologies that support the development and evaluation of medicines¹⁷⁶.

The following subsections summarise the current state, the gaps and the potential path forward for using *in silico* evidence for regulatory evaluation of drugs and medical devices.

3.6.1 Qualification pathway for medicinal products

Current state

The EMA's novel methodology qualification process boasts several strengths, including transparency through published opinions and support letters, fostering innovation, proactive dialogue, and a flexible framework accommodating a wide range of methodologies.

To our observation, **about four modelling and simulation methodologies have had certain success with the qualification procedure** through a novel methodology qualification pathway. This includes

- (a) 2024 - Universal Immune System Simulator - Tuberculosis disease model (UISS)¹⁷⁷ for studying immune system dynamics in Tuberculosis and for use in vaccine development¹⁷⁸.
- (b) 2022 - Prognostic Covariate Adjustment (PROCOVA™)¹⁷⁹, a regulatory framework to employ patient-specific prognostic scores obtained from computer models to lower trial sizes for use in Phase II and II trials¹⁸⁰.

¹⁷⁴ For Medical Device Development Tool program - Center for devices and radiological Health (CDRH) - <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/medical-device-development-tools-mddt>

¹⁷⁵ FDA's – Qualification program for Drug Development Tools <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/development-approval-process-drugs/drug-development-tools-ddts>

¹⁷⁶ EMA's Qualification program for research and development of pharmaceuticals – 'Qualification of novel methodologies for medicine development' - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development>

¹⁷⁷ EMA Letter of support for Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis disease model - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/letter-support-universal-immune-system-simulator-tuberculosis-disease-model-uiss-tb-dr_en.pdf

¹⁷⁸ News report - VPH Institute - A new era for tuberculosis vaccines is coming- <https://www.vph-institute.org/news/a-new-era-for-tuberculosis-vaccines-is-coming.html>

¹⁷⁹ EMA Qualification opinion for Prognostic Covariate Adjustment (PROCOVA™) - 2022 <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-development/scientific-advice-protocol-assistance/opinions-letters-support-qualification-novel-methodologies-medicine-development#prognostic-covariate-adjustment-procova-8081>

¹⁸⁰ Press Release and News article - EMA qualifies Unlearn's AI-driven approach for smaller trials - <https://www.clinicaltrialsarena.com/news/ema-qualifies-unlearn-approach/> - <https://www.unlearn.ai/blog/success-is-never-a-straight-line--reflecting-on-our-ema-draft-qualification-opinion>

- (c) 2022 -Clinical trial simulation platform for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy¹⁸¹ for accelerating therapeutic progress and establishing drug development tools better to inform clinical trial protocols for rare disease¹⁸².
- (d) 2020/21 - Mobilise-D digital mobility outcomes as monitoring biomarkers for use in clinical trials¹⁸³, which allows digital readout of walking as a measure of health¹⁸⁴.

Likewise, we noted the following modelling and simulation-related guidance documents and Question & Answers styled documents from EMA. They support the qualification pathways related to **physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation**¹⁸⁵, as well as clarify EMA's position on **Modelling and simulation**¹⁸⁶ and **digital technology-based methodologies**¹⁸⁷.

Gaps and potential next steps

While the EMA's qualification process offers a flexible approach, its current framework may not be optimally suited for evaluating novel methodologies such as *in silico* trials. To enhance the qualification process for these innovative approaches, several key improvements are warranted. To this end, EMA working parties like [Methodological Working Party](#) and [Quality Innovation Group \(QIG\)](#) are starting to go beyond the PBPK – Quantitative System Pharmacology (QSP) approaches. The consideration of complex mechanistic models, including the likes of computational fluid dynamics, agent-based models and artificial intelligence, for drug development, process evaluation and regulatory assessment is encouraging and needs further attention¹⁸⁸.

Expertise matters in regulating *In silico* Trials

¹⁸¹ EMA Letter of support of model-based clinical trial simulation platform (CTSP) for Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/letter-support-model-based-clinical-trial-simulation-platform-ctsp-duchenne-muscular-dystrophy_en.pdf

¹⁸² Press Release – Critical Path Institute C-Path Receives Letter of Support from EMA on Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy Clinical Trial Simulation Platform - <https://c-path.org/c-path-receives-letter-of-support-from-ema-on-duchenne-muscular-dystrophy-clinical-trial-simulation-platform/>

¹⁸³ EMA Letter of support for Mobilise-D digital mobility outcomes as monitoring biomarkers - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/letter-support-mobilise-d-digital-mobility-outcomes-monitoring-biomarkers-follow_en.pdf

¹⁸⁴ News reports - One step closer: digital readouts of walking as a measure of health - Mobilise-D's letter of support from the EMA is not only a nod to the promise of their research – it shows how important it is to connect with regulators early <https://www.ihf.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets/mobilise-d>

¹⁸⁵ Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) - Reporting of physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling and simulation - Scientific guideline - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/reporting-physiologically-based-pharmacokinetic-pbpbk-modelling-simulation-scientific-guideline>

¹⁸⁶ EMA's position on M&S: Question and answers - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/research-and-development/scientific-guidelines/clinical-pharmacology-and-pharmacokinetics/modelling-and-simulation-questions-and-answers>

¹⁸⁷ EMA's position digital technology based methodologies: Questions and answers: Qualification of digital technology-based methodologies to support approval of medicinal products – 04/06/2020 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/questions-and-answers-qualification-digital-technology-based-methodologies-support-approval-medicinal-products_en.pdf

¹⁸⁸ EMA, Quality Innovation Group, Preliminary QIG Considerations regarding Pharmaceutical Process Models, (2024). https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/preliminary-qig-considerations-regarding-pharmaceutical-process-models_en.pdf

While the establishment of the [Methodological Working Party](#) is a welcome development for the *in silico* community, a critical step remains: formally separating the panels responsible for drug marketing authorisation from those evaluating novel methodologies. This separation is essential for several reasons:

- **Separation:** Merging the methodology qualification pathway evaluations with traditional drug marketing authorisation processes may inadvertently overlook or underweight the specific considerations relevant to *in silico* methods. The current absence of separation underscores the need for specialised expertise in regulating complex technologies like *In silico* Trials. A dedicated panel focused on methodological advancements can streamline the review process for *in silico* approaches, ensuring timely and transparent evaluations.
- **Interdisciplinary expertise:** Evaluating innovative methods like *In silico* Trials requires a deep understanding of these technologies and their unique challenges. The panel appointed to advise on the qualification of new methodologies should enhance its interdisciplinary character by incorporating experts from diverse backgrounds, including computer scientists, bioengineers, and biophysicists, alongside life scientists. This recommendation is supported by the current limited diversity within the Scientific Advice Working Party (SAWP). While recognising the challenges of fostering effective collaboration among diverse disciplines, interdisciplinarity within regulatory agencies is crucial, given the increasingly interdisciplinary nature of modern medicine.

By establishing a separate panel for evaluating innovative methodologies, the EMA can ensure the efficient and rigorous assessment of *in silico* trial solutions while capitalising on the expertise of a dedicated group of specialists. This would significantly advance the regulatory landscape for these transformative technologies.

3.6.2 [Qualification pathway for medical devices](#)

Current state

Until recently, **early dialogue with regulators**, such as Notified Bodies or the EMA, regarding medical device development was limited. Recognising the need for improved communication and guidance, the EMA has initiated two pilot programs to provide scientific advice for medical devices. The EMA offers pilot programs for high-risk medical devices (Class III, Class IIb)¹⁸⁹ and orphan medical devices¹⁹⁰, extending established scientific advice pathways to these specific categories. These pilot programs serve as a learning exercise for all stakeholders, including the EMA, manufacturers, and notified bodies. The scientific advice procedures generally mirror those established for medicinal products. According to EMA, The pilot programs are partly ended and will be reviewed to assess their effectiveness to organise regular scientific advice for medical devices in 2025.

Gaps and challenges

The current regulatory landscape within the European Union presents significant challenges for the adoption of *in silico* trials in medical device development. Europe currently lacks harmonised standards (like ASME

¹⁸⁹ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/medical-devices#high-risk-medical-devices-13044>

¹⁹⁰ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/medical-devices#scientific-advice-pilot-for-high-risk-medical-devices-13045>

V&V¹⁹¹), guidance (like FDA CM& guidance^{192,193}), and recognised regulatory programs (like FDA CM&S program¹⁹⁴) for evaluating *in silico* methodologies, creating uncertainty for health technology developers and also challenging for Notified Bodies. Notified Bodies, subject to rigorous audits by National Competent Authorities (NCA), often limit their scope to explicit references within the EU-MDR¹⁹⁵ and Medical Device Coordination Group's (MDCG) guidance.

While the MDCG has clarified the use of structured dialogue for pre-submission to reduce ambiguities for developers, its recent implementation and cautious approach among Notified Bodies in using them for *in silico* technologies¹⁹⁶ limit its effectiveness. Furthermore, existing guidance documents, such as MDCG 2020-6¹⁹⁷ and MDCG 2024-10¹⁹⁸, either do not explicitly list modelling data as a valid data source or restrict its use to non-clinical evidence.

The decentralised oversight of individual Notified Bodies by National Competent Authorities (NCAs) within the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG), aims to improve implementation challenges. However, the *in silico* medicine community has limited access to these crucial forums. This restricted access hinders effective communication and collaboration with regulators, preventing the community from voicing concerns and contributing to the development of guidance documents that could potentially address the unique challenges of *in silico* evidence. The above constraints, coupled with a lack of visibility and acknowledgment of these critical implementation gaps, significantly hinder the progression of *in silico* trial solutions to be considered as a viable source of regulatory evidence for evaluating the safety and effectiveness of medical devices, in Europe.

¹⁹¹Assessing Credibility of Computational Modeling through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices V&V 40 – 2018. ASME, 2018. 60p. ISBN: 9780791872048.

¹⁹² 2023 -US FDA - Guidance for Industry and Food and Drug Administration Staff; Docket Number: FDA-2021-D-0980; <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/assessing-credibility-computational-modeling-and-simulation-medical-device-submissions>

¹⁹³ 2016 - US FDA - Reporting of Computational Modeling Studies in Medical Device Submissions – Guidance FDA-2013-D-1530 - <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/reporting-computational-modeling-studies-medical-device-submissions>

¹⁹⁴ US FDA - Credibility of Computational Models Program: Research on Computational Models and Simulation Associated with Medical Devices - <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/medical-device-regulatory-science-research-programs-conducted-osel/credibility-computational-models-program-research-computational-models-and-simulation-associated>

¹⁹⁵ EU-MDR – Medical Device Regulation - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj>

¹⁹⁶ A recent public webinar ([‘Structured Dialogue – How to Engage with Notified Bodies?’](#) – dt. 4 October, 2024 by RQM+) with the leadership team of three prominent Notified Bodies (Panellists included Dr. A Stange (TÜV SÜD), T. Pattern (GMED), A Laan (IVD, BSI) – session moderated by J. Kutty, [RQM+](#)) highlighted this concern. When explicitly questioned about the consideration of *in silico* trial evidence, the panel unanimously indicated that it falls under "emerging technologies," outside their current remit, and suggested seeking guidance from the European Medicines Agency (EMA).

¹⁹⁷ MDCG 2020-6 (April 2020) – MDCG - Clinical evidence needed for medical devices previously CE marked under Directives 93/42/EEC or 90/385/EEC – lists a summary of considerations related to use of clinical and non-clinical data sources in Appendix II, which conspicuously does not explicitly list modelling data, but even more indicates simulated user as not clinical data.

¹⁹⁸ ‘MDCG 2024-10 (June 2024)- MDCG Guidance on Clinical Evaluation of orphan medical devices — page 10 – ‘Useful source of non-clinical data can include - Results of laboratory and animal tests; Data from computer modelling and simulated use testing, including software-based models, 3D printed models, and other physical models;...’ citing Non-clinical data’ is understood as any relevant data that does not meet the MDR definition of clinical data Per MDR Article 2(48)

Potential next steps

The following list outlines several concrete steps to address the pressing regulatory science challenges within the medical device sector. These considerations focus on: (a) Revising EU-MDR to accommodate future innovations, particularly in emerging technologies like *in silico* trial solutions instead of merely tackling only the pressing MDR implementation issues. Explicitly including *in silico* trials and modelling & simulation within the EU-MDR provides clarity and reduces ambiguity for developers and notified bodies. (b) Consider broadening the scope of EMA's scientific advice program for high-risk medical devices, including emerging technologies. (c) Ensuring those evaluating medical devices possess the necessary knowledge and expertise in emerging technologies. Training conformity assessment professionals from notified bodies and regulatory affairs professionals from industry is crucial for developing the future *in silico* workforce. (d) Facilitating the participation of representatives of *in silico* medicine community in new emerging technologies working groups of the MDCG forum.

Last but not least, creating public repositories and catalogues to offer standardised testing environments and sandboxes to establish validation of *in silico* models in a non-burdensome manner for developers and regulators goes a long way in support, especially for small-medium enterprises. One could draw inspiration from the FDA's successful model of regulatory Science Catalogue¹⁹⁹, which is widely being used in actual regulatory submissions, saving time and resources for addressing the key question of safety²⁰⁰.

3.7 Theme 6: Engaging stakeholders within *in silico* trials

3.7.1 Current state

The field of *In silico Medicine* has entered into a transformational phase of becoming part of real-life applications. Within this landscape, active **engagement with diverse stakeholders** such as patients, clinicians, industry leaders, professional societies, governing bodies like regulators and health technology assessors is imperative, to ensure the alignment of the development with the values, needs and expectations of all involved parties. Furthermore, it is critical to **understand the ethical, legal and social implications** of the *In*

¹⁹⁹ FDA's – [Qualification program for Medical Device Development Tools \(MDDT\)](#) and [Catalog of Regulatory Science Tools to Help Assess New Medical Devices](#) in the absence of MDDT

²⁰⁰ In May 2024, the then Director of Center for Devices and Radiological Health, Ed Margerrison presented the FDA's regulator's strategy to leverage standardization as a means to support small business innovation. The CDRH Director, explained that regulatory science tools help reduce the persistent questions on testing and the protocol of testing, by using these tools as standardized test environment. Thus, sparing the valuable time and focus for the reviewers to concentrate on how good the device is. Thus, driving innovation- Extracts from the Regulatory Education for Industry (REdI) Annual Conference Innovation in Medical Product Development May 29-30, 2024 - <https://sbiaevents.com/redi2024/>

in silico Medicine technologies. Meaningful stakeholder engagement does not equal dissemination or communication, but really involves stakeholders in the development of technologies^{201,202,203,204}.

Within the ISW project²⁰⁵, stakeholder engagement was not simply an afterthought, but constituted a foundational principle from the start. During the writing stage of the research proposal, social scientists were actively involved, working alongside legal experts and modelling teams. This allowed an extensive stakeholder engagement approach (Desk review and Delphi Study²⁰⁶, focus groups²⁰⁷, surveys²⁰⁸, workshops²⁰⁹, INFOKIT's²¹⁰) to be set up from the start. The approach was implemented within the methodological framework of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)^{211,212,213,214}, aiming to anticipate and address the ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) during the development of the *in silico* technologies.

Recognising that the concept of *in silico* trials remains relatively far removed from the lived experiences of many people, the focus group discussions intentionally broadened their scope to explore perceptions of the wider field of *in silico* medicine, once again illustrating the reflexive mindset throughout the project, constantly questioning assumptions and adjusting engagement practices to ensure it remained meaningful, accessible and relevant. Importantly, the social science partners did not only conduct these engagement efforts, but also produced detailed reports on their outcomes, followed with reflection workshops^{215,216}.

²⁰¹ Contin, M., et al. An *in silico* Medicine Info Kit for Effective Stakeholder Engagement. Zenodo, 2024, doi:10.5281/zenodo.13760091.

²⁰² Geris, L., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Rangarajan, J. R., Biasin, E., Van Hoyweghen, I., & Viceconti, M. (2024). Policy brief: Accelerating the uptake of *in silico* trials in healthcare. DOI: doi:10.5281/zenodo.14534366.

²⁰³ Rangarajan, J. R., et al. The *In Silico* Medicine Info Kit - Vphi. Zenodo, 20 Dec. 2024, doi:10.5281/zenodo.14536119.

²⁰⁴ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

²⁰⁵ *In silico* World has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016503. For more information on the project, see <https://insilico.world/>

²⁰⁶ Van Oudheusden, M., Lesage, R., Geris, L., Van Hoyweghen, I. (2023). Internal Survey for ISW General Assembly: A Delphi Approach - <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740390>

²⁰⁷ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., Geris, L., Van Hoyweghen, I. (2023). *In silico* World WP5 Stakeholder Engagement - Focus Groups Analysis Report - <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740366>

²⁰⁸ Lesage R, Van Oudheusden M, Schievano S, Van Hoyweghen I, Geris L, Capelli C. Mapping the use of computational modelling and simulation in clinics: A survey. *Front Med Technol*. 2023 Apr 17;5:1125524. doi: 10.3389/fmedt.2023.1125524. PMID: 37138727; PMCID: PMC10150234.

²⁰⁹ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., Geris, L., and Van Hoyweghen, I. Rep. *In silico* World WP 5 Responsible Research and Innovation Workshop Report, 2023. Available via public repository: <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740365>.

²¹⁰ Rangarajan, J. R., et al. The *in silico* Medicine Info Kit - Vphi. Zenodo, 20 Dec. 2024, doi:10.5281/zenodo.14536119.

²¹¹ Zwart, H., Landeweerd, L., & van Rooij, A. (2014). Adapt or perish? Assessing the recent shift in the European research funding arena from 'ELSA' to 'RRI.' *Life Sciences, Society and Policy*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-014-0011-x>

²¹² Felt, U. (2014). Within, Across and Beyond: Reconsidering the Role of Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe. *Science as Culture*, 23(3), 384–396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505431.2014.926146>

²¹³ Felt, Ulrike. (2017). Chapter – “Responsible Research and Innovation” – In *Handbook of Genomics, Health and Society*. Publisher : Routledge.

²¹⁴ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

²¹⁵ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., Geris, L., and Van Hoyweghen, I. Rep. *In silico* World WP 5 Responsible Research and Innovation Workshop Report, 2023. Available via public repository: <https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740365>.

²¹⁶ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

3.7.2 Gaps and challenges

RRI in practice: lessons from the ISW project

Responsible Research and Innovation: only meaningful on paper? Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) was introduced as a way to make research and innovation processes more inclusive, reflexive, and responsive to different societal needs. While the top-down push for RRI has provided useful tools for conducting research responsibly and rendering the research institution more self-reflexive, its application has been a topic of debate among different STS scholars^{217,218,219,220,221,222}. One such discussion point is the lack of clear implementation of the RRI framework and the **risks of reducing RRI to mere checkboxes to secure research funding. Overlooked power dynamics within collaborations can result in the prioritisation of technical progress at the expense of socially responsible outcomes while excluding certain voices in the discussion and more.** Although these points highlight the frameworks' shortcomings, they do demonstrate strong reflexivity within the research domain, actively calling for a more concrete and effective interpretation and implementation of RRI²²³. Despite the significant investments in RRI in projects by the European Commission, there remains a **noticeable gap in their actual impact on R&I.**

The need for robust stakeholder engagement frameworks, **beyond sole deliberation and continuous funding is vital to engage society in a meaningful manner**, allowing citizens to influence decision-making processes in *In silico Medicine*. Project limitations, strict time and deadlines, and diversified motivations have been shown to limit meaningful RRI implementation, risk-reducing stakeholder engagement activities to checkboxes, and hindering its impact on the direction of R&I²²⁴. In this context, the extensive RRI framework in the ISW project offers a concrete example of how such integration can be pursued. The social science partners produced reports after each engagement activity, prompting the technical consortium members to reflect on the findings by raising critical questions. They also went a step further by turning the mirror inward, reflecting on their own role, positionality, and influence within the interdisciplinary collaboration. By embedding reflexivity as an ongoing practice rather than a one-time requirement, the ISW project aimed to actively overcome the tokenism often associated with RRI, and instead cultivated a space where ethical and societal considerations were treated as integral to the R&I process.

²¹⁷ Felt, U., Öchsner, S., Rae, R., & Osipova, E. (2023). Doing co-creation: power and critique in the development of a European health data infrastructure. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2023.2235931>

²¹⁸ Fisher, E. (2016). Framings and frameworks of responsible innovation. In *Journal of Responsible Innovation* (Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 185–187). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2016.1267418>

²¹⁹ Goñi, J. "Iñaki," Rodrigues, E., Parga, M. J., Illanes, M., & Millán, M. J. (2024). Tooling with ethics in technology: a scoping review of responsible research and innovation tools. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2360228>

²²⁰ van Oudheusden, M. (2014). Where are the politics in responsible innovation? European governance, technology assessments, and beyond. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2014.882097>

²²¹ van Oudheusden, M., & Shelley-Egan, C. (2021). RRI Futures: learning from a diversity of voices and visions. In *Journal of Responsible Innovation* (Vol. 8, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2021.1989656>

²²² Zwart, H., Landeweerd, L., & van Rooij, A. (2014). Adapt or perish? Assessing the recent shift in the European research funding arena from 'ELSA' to 'RRI.' *Life Sciences, Society and Policy*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40504-014-0011-x>

²²³ See Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in in silico medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

²²⁴ Felt, U., Öchsner, S., Rae, R., & Osipova, E. (2023). Doing co-creation: power and critique in the development of a European health data infrastructure. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2023.2235931>

3.7.3 *Potential next steps*

Drawing from the lessons learned from the implementation of RRI in the ISW project²²⁵ in close collaboration with social scientists, along with the general challenges connected to RRI, we would like to highlight the following key needs:

- **Impactful RRI should go beyond simply advancing R&I** at hand, not to be seen as a standalone requirement to secure funding, but as a genuine tool to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and address complex societal challenges inclusively. It should allow the freedom and space for researchers to take a step back, reflect, and open up R&I to diverse stakeholders. This means ensuring R&I effectively aligns with societal needs and becomes truly meaningful, even if that means slowing down the R&I process to make it more flexible, adaptive, and societally responsive.
- There is a **need for continued policy and financial support beyond individual projects, to which** investments are needed to empower researchers to make sense of RRI in their work and to create environments that provide the time and space for such engagements. At the same time, continued support is required for organisations and research teams to build expertise in RRI to implement its principles meaningfully.
- It is important to stress that meaningful RRI and the exploration of ELSI should not imply a divide between those conducting the technical research and those reflecting on the broader societal implications. Instead, investments should be made to overcome such a divide through institutional shifts that integrate reflexivity as a shared responsibility for all rather than solely outsourcing the task of doing RRI to Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)^{226,227}. As the social science partners argue in their reflexive peer-reviewed publication on their involvement in the project, interdisciplinary collaboration and long-term partnerships between academic fields should be institutionally supported and structurally embedded.
- A continuous culture of reflection: In order for RRI implementation to become meaningful, **a research culture should be fostered that values openness, prioritises true societal impact** over mere progress within project spaces, and understands the true value and complexities of RRI. This allows making time and space for reflection at every stage, and recognizing that responsible innovation sometimes requires slowing down to accommodate uncertainty and diverse viewpoints.

In addition to necessary work on stakeholder engagement and RRI, the **Ethics guidelines for Trustworthy AI**, developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI, can be applied to *In silico Medicine*. These guidelines outline seven key requirements for assessing the trustworthiness of AI systems: human agency and oversight; technical robustness and safety; privacy and data governance; transparency; diversity, non-discrimination and fairness; societal and environmental well-being; and accountability. These guidelines should, however,

²²⁵ Elisa Elhadj, Zita Van Horenbeeck, Elisa Lievrouw & Ine Van Hoyweghen (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

²²⁶ Felt, U. (2014). Within, Across and Beyond: Reconsidering the Role of Social Sciences and Humanities in Europe. *Science as Culture*, 23(3), 384–396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09505431.2014.926146>

²²⁷ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

address their abstract notions of trustworthiness and responsibility, focus on human-centred approaches, and be complemented by regulatory frameworks for robust and context-applicable implementations.

4 Next steps to advance *in silico* trial methodologies

With the previous sections outlining the current landscape of *in silico* trial solutions, including the current state, gaps and underrepresentation, as well as potential solutions, this section formulates four focus areas for future work.

4.1 Focus 1: policies & regulations

4.1.1 Acknowledge policy gaps

While recent policies have encouraged the advancement of *in silico* trial methodologies in healthcare, their value is often recognised primarily within specific application areas. It is crucial to expand this recognition beyond traditional uses, such as solely supporting non-clinical research. *In silico* trials have the potential to significantly contribute to the 3R principle by reducing, refining, and replacing animal experimentation as well as human experimentation in order to derisk the development and evaluation of medicinal products and medical devices, as well as for advancing research.

4.1.2 Limit misrepresentation

A trend observed is a decline in the explicit mention of *in silico* trials and the use of modelling and simulation in drug development and evaluation within recent policy documents (e.g. EMA Regulatory Science Strategy 2020²²⁸ versus 2025 mid-term report²²⁹, EMA Network Strategy 2025²³⁰ versus Network Strategy 2028²³¹). While these methodologies were explicitly addressed in policies in the last decade, they are now **increasingly subsumed under broader research and regulatory frameworks, often without or limited explicit mention**. Furthermore, a significant issue is the tendency to erroneously categorise all *In silico Medicine* methodologies under artificial intelligence and machine learning, despite the fact that AI is just one (powerful) subset of these

²²⁸ European Medicines Agency published 'EMA Regulatory Science to 2025 - Strategic reflection' – March 31, 2020. Accessed via: https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/ema-regulatory-science-2025-strategic-reflection_en.pdf

²²⁹ EMA's Regulatory Science Strategy to 2025 - Mid-point achievements to end 2022. Published on 22/03/2023 - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/emas-regulatory-science-strategy-2025-mid-point-achievements-end-2022_en.pdf

²³⁰ EMA's European Union Medicines Agencies Network **Strategy to 2025** - Protecting public health at a time of rapid change - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/european-union-medicines-agencies-network-strategy-2025-protecting-public-health-time-rapid-change_en.pdf

²³¹ EMA's Seizing opportunities in a changing medicines landscape: The European medicines agencies network **strategy 2028 (draft)** - https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/seizing-opportunities-changing-medicines-landscape-european-medicines-agencies-network-strategy-2028-draft_en.pdf

broader modelling approaches²³². While the modelling and simulation methodologies, including AI, are often valued for data processing and drawing inference, their potential for predictive capabilities seems to be understated in policy documents and reflection papers²³³.

On a broader note beyond policy documents, **AI-washing** is a significant concern, as overhyping AI and presenting it as a monolithic computer modelling solution to all healthcare challenges is misleading and potentially dangerous. The AI-based modelling technique is one among many *in silico* methodologies (e.g. physics-based modelling)²³⁴. Engaging with the broader biomedical scientific community, alongside data scientists, is critical to understanding the limitations of AI in healthcare and identifying and combining complementary approaches. As a path forward, active work is required to:

- **Demystify AI** by promoting a nuanced understanding of AI, emphasising its strengths and limitations within the healthcare context.
- **Emphasise the limitations of the AI approaches**, particularly while addressing situations with limited data to train, such as rare diseases and marginalised populations.
- **Advocate for a multi-methodological or hybrid approach** by encouraging using a diverse range of *In silico Medicine* methodologies to address their individual limitations.
- **Educate and sensitise governing actors**, namely policymakers, regulators and decision-makers, on the diverse landscape of *In silico Medicine* methodologies, moving beyond the limited view of AI as the sole solution.

4.1.3 Initiate unified strategy and policymaking for drugs and devices

Europe's current separation of its regulatory frameworks for drugs and medical devices poses challenges for emerging and adopting innovative methodologies. This slows down the process and negatively impacts Europe's innovative competitiveness in comparison to the US, where the FDA provides unified qualification advice covering both drug and medical device development. Therefore, we propose broadening the scope of the working parties to encompass all medical products, being them drugs or medical devices, to streamline the regulatory process across Europe and make them more efficient and accessible for emerging technologies.

4.2 Focus 2: Regulatory pathways

4.2.1 Acknowledge uncertainties and evidence gaps across health continuum

The framework for assessing the credibility of a model indicates that "No model will be a perfect picture of reality but - still - it may serve for a certain Context of Use and associated risk given that it fulfils a certain set

²³² Geris Liesbet, Rousseau Cécile F., Noailly Jerome, et al., (2022). WHITE PAPER: the role of Artificial Intelligence within *In silico Medicine*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8064147>

²³³ EMA's Reflection paper on the use of artificial intelligence in the lifecycle of medicines - <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/use-artificial-intelligence-ai-medicinal-product-lifecycle>

²³⁴ Geris Liesbet, Rousseau Cécile F., Noailly Jerome, et al., (2022). WHITE PAPER: the role of Artificial Intelligence within *In silico Medicine*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8064147>

of quality criteria”²³⁵. On this note, it is important first to acknowledge that **uncertainties exist across the healthcare continuum**. Regardless of the evidence source (*in vivo*, *in vitro*, *in silico*, clinical trials), uncertainties persist throughout the healthcare lifecycle, from development to post-market surveillance.

The dilemma of quantifying uncertainties.

The current approach to regulatory acceptance of digital evidence is overly cautious and potentially detrimental to healthcare progress. While acknowledging the need for caution, it is important to emphasise that the traditional evidence sources, despite inherent uncertainties, have been accepted due to their long history of use and implicit “real-world testing”. Conversely, uncertainties of traditional evidence (e.g. generated from animal testing) are even difficult to quantify and map with clinical endpoints or outcomes objectively. Emerging digital evidence paradigms, on the other hand, offer the potential of extensively quantifying the digital evidence that they generate. Ironically, this objective quantification of uncertainty itself seems to contribute to the hesitation of regulators to embrace digital evidence.

Wait-and-see approach amidst changing times

The existing regulatory frameworks' immediate response is to be cautious and demand parallel evidence generation using both traditional and digital approaches until they gain confidence. Regulatory and HTA decision-makers have historically followed this “wait-and-see” doctrine, expecting “perfect evidence” to emerge over time. While this approach is conceived in the best interest of public health and well-being, we are in a changing time. Big, disruptive (not necessarily fast) solutions that impact the status quo are needed to solve major problems. As the EU pharmaceutical strategy report²³⁶ highlights, today's reality is one of increasing health emergencies, including pandemics, anti-microbial resistance, and a barrage of comorbid chronic conditions. As outlined in the introduction, moving from “reactive” to “preventive” health systems, offering more “health” than “care”, and paving the way for “healthy ageing” are now indispensable, according to the EU-OECD – Health at a Glance report 2024²³⁷.

While the historical “**wait-and-see**” approach is understandable, it is becoming increasingly **impractical due to not only economic and time constraints** (increased costs and durations for parallel evidence generation) but also its **detrimental impact on healthcare systems**. This approach **delays access to potentially safer medical products** that could **improve health and move us beyond simply treating diseases**.

Another reason why the wait-and-see approach is unwise is that it relies on the presumption that the underlying healthcare provision models are and will remain stable in the near future. This is not the case, due to the ageing of the EU population, and the associated growing demand for care; there is a desperate need to reduce the unit cost of care if we want to protect the universal healthcare model that has historically contributed to the social justice model of the union. We need chapter drugs and medical devices, and one

²³⁵ Geris Liesbet, Rousseau Cécile F., Noailly Jerome, et al., (2022). WHITE PAPER: the role of Artificial Intelligence within *In silico Medicine*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8064147>

²³⁶ A pharmaceutical strategy for Europe, adopted 25, November 2020 - European Commission communication - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0761>

²³⁷ OECD/European Commission (2024), Health at a Glance: Europe 2024: State of Health in the EU Cycle, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b3704e14-en>

effective way to achieve this are more “intelligent” pathways for regulatory derisking of medical products and more personalised provision of care. So there is no time to waste, we need the type of innovation *In silico* Trials promises today, not tomorrow.

4.2.2 Limit disparities amongst evidence bases

Existing policies tend to unfairly prioritise certain evidence types (e.g., clinical trials) over others, such as *in silico* evidence. Moreover, ***in silico* evidence is often miscategorised** as "non-clinical," limiting its potential to be considered for "de-risking" human testing and unnecessarily exposing research subjects. As a way forward,

- Healthcare policies and regulations should recognise the value of combining evidence from various sources (*in vivo*, *in vitro*, *in silico*, clinical trials) to address uncertainties and improve decision-making.
- Reclassify *in silico* evidence to appropriately reflect its potential role in de-risking human testing and reducing the need for unnecessary animal or human experimentation.
- Promote a more nuanced approach to evidence evaluation, where diverse sources of evidence are used to cover the never-ending story of evidence gaps in downstream decision-making.

The evolving healthcare landscape, characterised by the emergence of novel digital technologies like *In silico Medicine*, necessitates a dynamic and integrated approach to evidence generation and evaluation. This approach requires acknowledging the strengths and limitations of all available evidence sources, including *in silico* methods, to address uncertainties and improve decision-making effectively.

As an example of the dynamic nature of evidence used in health systems, a recent policy symposium at the European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies titled 'Leveraging evidence to transform Health Systems'²³⁸, highlighted a critical point: the pursuit of “perfect” evidence for informed decision-making is often unrealistic. This was acknowledged by a diverse group of stakeholders, including representatives from Health Policy institutions (OECD, WHO, European Observatory), policymakers (EC) and patient organisations. On this note, the leadership of the European Patient Forum passionately advocated for a different approach²³⁹. Instead of prioritising the search for "perfect" evidence, the audience emphasised the importance of establishing a shared set of values and principles within the healthcare community. These values and principles should guide the evidence quest rather than the current practice of pursuing evidence in a more ad hoc manner.

²³⁸ “Leveraging evidence to transform health systems” - Hybrid Policy Symposium (10 Dec 2024) at the European Health Observatory on Health System and Policies (presided by the representatives from WHO Regional office for Europe, EC DG SANTE, Leadership team of European Observatory), where speakers explored the types of evidence policymakers need and the kinds of knowledge-brokering that can help them translate evidence into health system transformation.

²³⁹ Anecdotally, while listening to and participating in the debate, Anca Toma, Executive Director of the European Patients' Forum (EPF), advocated for a framework that establishes a community of practice. This community would consider evidence from all sources – as long as it resonates with shared values and community principles – for evaluation. This approach, she argued, would help reduce uncertainty and drive more informed decision-making. This observation was acknowledged and considered by distinguished leaders from the European Commission (EC), the World Health Organization (WHO), and the observatory.

4.2.3 Accelerate the integration of digital evidence

A proactive and pragmatic approach to the regulatory acceptance of digital evidence in healthcare is the need of the hour. This approach should (a) prioritise the development of robust frameworks for quantifying and communicating the uncertainties associated with digital evidence, (b) establish clear and tailored pathways for regulatory approval of digital evidence, with additional consideration for tackling the pressing health challenges and finally, (c) investing in research and development to support the generation and validation of high-quality digital evidence. Collectively, these have the potential to ensure safe and effective integration of these innovative *in silico* evidence to provide valuable insights early in the development process, supporting better trial design, identifying potential safety issues and informing decisions on target populations and outcomes to study.

4.3 Focus 3: Implementations & institutions

4.3.1 Acknowledge implementation gaps

Policies on 'emerging technologies' are as they should be strategic and visionary, and they offer big solutions for big problems. However, they need to be backed up with regulations and pragmatic implementation mechanisms in the form of guidelines, expedited channels, and pathways to facilitate open dialogue for the first generation of innovations from a domain.

Early dialogue with regulators and health technology assessment bodies should be expanded beyond its current focus on medicines and high-risk medical devices to encompass the broader spectrum of health technologies, including *in silico* trial solutions.

4.3.2 Moving beyond cherry-picking: Model types, application areas and pathways

While the legislative frameworks are drafted broadly, the implementations are limited to cherry-picking which type of models are of regulators' interest and for which application areas. While ostensibly permitting the use of modelling in drug development, current regulations and implementation guidance often impose significant limitations that hinder its widespread adoption. These limitations include: (a) modelling being confined to pre-clinical settings; (b) Guidance and implementation could favour specific modelling approaches, such as physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) or quantitative systems pharmacology (QSP) models while excluding or limiting other potentially valuable advanced modelling techniques. This can lead to "cherry-picking" of models, guidance and pathways that fit within the regulator's knowledge and expectations rather than selecting the most appropriate models for the specific research question.

Current practices of regulatory interaction seem to favour pathways destined for mainstream market approval applications, often requiring extensive clinical validation. There is a lack of flexibility to encourage early-stage dialogue with researchers and developers of emerging technologies, where open discussion is crucial for advancing regulatory science and facilitating better evidence-generation.

4.3.3 Need for EU vision and institutions that nurture and govern emerging technologies.

There is fragmentation, mainly due to the current lack of harmonisation in implementing regulations across EU member states. To address this fragmentation, the *in silico* community proposes the establishment of an **overarching institute or central authority to oversee and guide the implementation of much-needed regulations and guiding documents**. The call for such a unified authority could function as the missing link to engaging with regulatory agencies and streamlining technology-related discussions. This would help the ecosystem to evolve and bring down the barriers to emerging technologies, including *in silico* trials. This ask mirrors the need to align efforts made in the policy realm at European, as well as national and regional levels. The *in silico* medicine community suggests establishing a dedicated division within the European Medicines Agency (EMA) to facilitate the qualification of medical devices supported by *in silico* evidence. This division should comprise experts with diverse expertise in emerging healthcare advancements, including engineers, computer scientists, and physicists. Such an overarching body could potentially

- **Facilitate the unified application** of regulatory standards across member states, reducing redundancies and inconsistencies. This is especially advantageous for fostering and maintaining international collaborations, the foundation of *In silico Medicine*.
- **Serve as a clear central point of dialogue** between policymakers, regulators, industry leaders, and the research community.
- **Provide strategic direction** to align fragmented efforts, enabling the EU to remain unified and competitive in the global market for emerging medical technologies.

In his blog post on the ‘European Union: from the land of rights to the land of rules’, a key figure in the *in silico* domain, Prof. Marco Viceconti underscores this growing need for more policy coherence and adaptability when it comes to regulating emerging technologies, specifically *In silico Medicine*²⁴⁰.

4.4 Focus 4: building expertise and support for in silico community of practice

4.4.1 Acknowledge skills gap

The rapid evolution of *In silico Medicine* makes it difficult for researchers to keep up with advancements across all relevant areas. It is critical to acknowledge and address the critical skills gap that exists within the *in silico* community and among those professionals in the clinical practice, regulatory sphere and HTA domains who use, evaluate or assess *in silico* trials. This knowledge gap can obstruct the technical progression of *in silico* trials, but also effective communication and collaboration between scientists and other key stakeholders.

4.4.2 Need for interdisciplinary collaboration in project consortia

While the consideration of ethical and social implications of *in silico* medicine on the wider society are streamlined by policy frameworks like Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), their implementation gaps

²⁴⁰ For Prof. Marco Viceconti’s blogpost, see <http://secret-viceconti.blogspot.com/>

need attention. While the practical guidance for the RRI framework is fast evolving, Elhadj *et al.* echo the **risks of reducing RRI to mere checkboxes to secure research funding**. They further emphasise the need to address a **noticeable gap in their actual impact on R&I** by advocating for concrete and effective interpretation and implementation of RRI, especially in the context of *in silico* medicine²⁴¹.

Thus, the implementation of an iterative RRI framework ought to promote anticipatory thinking for all researchers in the *In silico Medicine* field. This also highlights the need for ongoing reflection and improvement when it comes to implementing RRI in and beyond research projects.

4.4.3 ***Support holistic training of workforce for fast-evolving ‘Digital (in silico)’ medicine world***

To mitigate the skills gap and overall development of the *in silico* community of practice (CoP),

- **Acknowledge and promote the multitude of information and educational materials**²⁴², tailored for the general public, for university students and (re)training professionals²⁴³ and handbooks on good practices²⁴⁴ for adopting computer modelling and simulation.
- **Open up RRI for more meaningful implementations**: this will require fostering a research culture that values openness to implement RRI, prioritises true societal impact over mere progress within project spaces, and understands the true value of RRI through reflection and collaboration. This will require investment in resources and creating environments that allow time and space for meaningful engagement with RRI.
- **Continuous funding and support of CoP**: Going beyond individual projects, dedicated funding streams and support are needed to foster long-term capacity-building. This also entails building expertise and promoting a broader understanding of the value of *in silico* medicine within the policy domain.

4.5 Summary

In summary, the field of *in silico* medicine and the utilisation of *in silico* trial solutions for de-risking medical products are rapidly evolving. However, the field faces several significant challenges that require dedicated attention to ensure its successful advancement. Sustaining long-term focus and community engagement is challenging due to the pressure for quick wins and the reliance on project-based funding for both technology and regulatory science advancements. Additionally, the fast emergence of sophisticated multi-scale computational models to tackle emerging healthcare challenges demands a robust ecosystem for the development, validation and deployment of *in silico* trial solutions. At the same time, legal and regulatory frameworks often lag behind technological advancements. Furthermore, a critical skills gap hinders effective

²⁴¹ See Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in *in silico* medicine, *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 11:1, DOI: [10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484](https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484)

²⁴² Examples of education and training materials: ISW initiative to formulate modular curricular for [Training the *in silico* trial workforce](#), ISW deliverable on Introductory Information Packages and Lecturing Materials for [Healthcare professionals](#) and VPH Institute's [In silico Medicine INFOKIT](#) for the research community to engage with key stakeholders.

²⁴³ Gheysen, L., & Vander Sloten, J. (2024). Training the *in silico* trials workforce. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14280732>

²⁴⁴ Viceconti, M., Luca, & Editors, E. (n.d.). *Synthesis Lectures on Biomedical Engineering Toward Good Simulation Practice Best Practices for the Use of Computational Modelling and Simulation in the Regulatory Process of Biomedical Products*.

communication and collaboration across diverse domains. Collectively, we strive for a **visionary and impactful strategy for the *in silico* medicine field**, underpinned by **robust policies and effective implementation mechanisms**, facilitated by a **pragmatic and dynamic legislative framework**.

5 Outlook

This white paper aims to inform all stakeholders on the current landscape of *In silico Medicine*, with observations on the gaps and to present the needs and potential opportunities to reap the benefits for patients and the wider society. More specifically, this document seeks to provide **guidance and information to a wide range of stakeholders interested in the policy and regulatory landscape** surrounding developing, validating, and implementing *In silico Medicine* technologies.

These identify the relevant policy-level considerations on *in silico* trials and necessary changes to support the growth and integration of *in silico* trial methodologies in the healthcare system. By addressing these recommendations, together with policymakers, an environment can be created that fosters confidence, supports innovation, and accelerates the adoption of *in silico* trials, ultimately benefiting European healthcare systems and societies at large.

By focusing on the regulatory science strategy, policies and necessary legislative pathways to drive the qualification of *in silico* trial solutions as regulatory science tools across the entire drug and device spectrum, we aim to pave the way for:

- **De-risking healthcare technology development:** Enabling safer and more effective products.
- **Transforming evidence generation:** Addressing the evolving evidence needs of decision-makers, across the healthcare continuum.
- **Driving digital transformation:** Accelerating the adoption of innovative *in silico* technologies in healthcare.

Overall, **recognising that digital evidence generated from *in silico* modelling and simulation**, including AI predictors, has the potential to act as a replacement for traditional physical experiments is paramount. Subsequently, accelerating the integration of digital evidence can facilitate the technology developers to generate evidence relevant to both regulatory evaluation on safety and efficacy and HTA's emphasis on relative effectiveness, which are both critical to **get the patients safe and better cures – The vision of *In Silico World!***

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7 Appendix 1 – *In silico* World Project Context

A white paper is an extensive, focused, and straightforward document that presents a specific issue, well-argued with literature, statements, and the work already done to resolve this issue, and presents several opportunities to tackle the issue further. Such a report aims to bring awareness to decision-makers about a particular challenge while unpacking its complexities, providing clear insights and arguments, and serving as a guide for informed policy choices. This white paper, written in the context of the Horizon 2020 project *In Silico* World (ISW)²⁴⁵, aims to **guide policymakers through the field of *In silico* Medicine by highlighting its opportunities for European healthcare systems while addressing the challenges and exploring how targeted policy measures can help overcome these barriers.**

After introducing the field of *In silico* Medicine, the paper delves into the specific area of ***in silico* trial solutions**. The reason is that the Horizon Project ISW concentrated primarily on “overcoming the barriers to accelerate the uptake of *in silico* trials in healthcare”. At the same time, the broader perspective of *In silico* Medicine is retained to ensure greater consistency, accessibility, and relevance for policymakers, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the field as it advances.

7.1 Context: The *In silico* World project

The *In Silico* World (ISW) project¹ (2020-2024), funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101016503, is geared to facilitate the uptake of *In silico* Trial Technologies for the development and regulatory approval of medicinal products and devices. By **addressing critical barriers to the widespread implementation of *in silico* trials**, the project seeks to drive innovative solutions that foster acceptance and trust among key stakeholders, including the medical industry, regulatory bodies, clinicians, healthcare providers, payers, and policymakers.

A key ambition of ISW is **to shift the paradigm of traditional trials by integrating *in silico* trial technologies into the regulatory framework**, thereby establishing robust regulatory pathways for their use. This approach is expected to significantly reduce the time and costs associated with developing and approving new medical products while maintaining or improving safety standards compared to traditional methods²⁴⁶. One transformative aspect of these innovations is their potential to enhance learning. By providing **causal insights into why a product may lack safety or efficacy**, *in silico* trial technologies can inform redevelopment strategies, eliminating the need for a complete restart, a common drawback of current practices²⁴⁷. The ISW project aims to achieve its goals by lowering seven self-identified barriers to this broader uptake of *In silico* Trials (discussed further in Section 8.3): (1) lack of advanced models; (2) lack of independent collection of validation data; (3) lack of clear pathways for regulatory approval; (4) lack of informed stakeholders; (5) poor scalability and efficiency; (6) lack of sustainable business models; and, (7) lack of a trained workforce.

²⁴⁵ For more information on the *In silico* World project, please visit <https://insilico.world/>

²⁴⁶ Passini E, Britton OJ, Lu HR, et al. Human *in silico* drug trials demonstrate higher accuracy than animal models in predicting clinical pro-arrhythmic cardiotoxicity. *Front Physiol* 2017;8:668

²⁴⁷ Faris O, Shuren J. An FDA viewpoint on unique considerations for medical-device clinical trials. *N Engl J Med* 2017;376(14): 1350–7.

7.2 Need for *in silico* trials

Safety and efficacy assessments traditionally relied on experimental approaches such as *in vitro* and *ex vivo* studies, animal testing, and human clinical trials. However, several shortcomings of these traditional methods underscore the need for computational models in the evidence-generation process. *In vitro* and *ex vivo* testing can be time-consuming, animal experimentation raises significant ethical concerns, and clinical trials are costly and lengthy²⁴⁸. These challenges delay market entry and inflate costs, often resulting in higher prices for end-users. Furthermore, these traditional methods can exacerbate disparities, as they frequently fail to account for diversity in gender, age, ethnicity, rare conditions, and socioeconomic status²⁴⁹.

Additionally, conventional experimental approaches are often hypothesis-driven, aiming to demonstrate the absence of safety or efficacy, rather than providing actionable insights to improve the design and performance of medical products²⁵⁰. These challenges highlight the need for innovative solutions in healthcare, positioning *in silico* trial technologies as a suitable alternative to overcome the limitations of traditional approaches. In particular, *In silico* Trials offers opportunities^{251,252,253,254} for:

- **Cost savings:** potentially reducing the need for expensive and time-consuming clinical trials.
- **Simulation of diverse scenarios:** allowing for testing under conditions that may not be feasible or ethical with human subjects.
- **Exploration of wider patient populations:** enabling investigation in groups like those with rare diseases or paediatric patients without exposing them to risk.
- **Streamline regulatory evaluation of medical products:** by reducing, refining or replacing the physical clinical trials, through use of in-silico simulations.
 - **Example:** Safe magnetic resonance imaging with pacemaker^{255,256}; Virtual patient models for medical device evaluation²⁵⁷
- **Augment clinical trial design:** by generating virtual patients with specific characteristics.

²⁴⁸ Favre P, Bischoff J. Identifying the patient harms to include in an *in silico* clinical trial. *Comput Methods Programs Biomed.* 2023 Nov;241:107735. doi: 10.1016/j.cmpb.2023.107735.

²⁴⁹ Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

²⁵⁰ Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform.* 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

²⁵¹ Viceconti, M., Cobelli, C., Haddad, T. et al. (2017) *In silico* assessment of biomedical products: the conundrum of rare but not so rare events in two case studies. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers. Part H: Journal of Engineering in Medicine*, 231 (5). pp. 455-466.

²⁵² Jean-Quartier, C., Jeanquartier, F., Jurisica, I., & Holzinger, A. (2018). *In silico* cancer research towards 3R. *BMC Cancer*, 18(1), 408–408. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-018-4302-0>

²⁵³ Francesco Pappalardo, Giulia Russo, Flora Musuamba Tshinanu, Marco Viceconti, *In silico* clinical trials: concepts and early adoptions, *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, Volume 20, Issue 5, September 2019, Pages 1699–1708, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bby043>

²⁵⁴ Faris O, Shuren J. An FDA viewpoint on unique considerations for medical-device clinical trials. *N Engl J Med* 2017;376(14): 1350–7.

²⁵⁵ Safe magnetic resonance imaging scanning of patients with cardiac rhythm devices: A role for computer modeling Wilkoff, Bruce L. et al. *Heart Rhythm*, Volume 10, Issue 12, 1815 - 1821

²⁵⁶ <https://www.dicardiology.com/product/medtronic-gets-ce-mark-mri-compatible-pacemaker>

²⁵⁷ Gosselin MC, Neufeld E, Moser H, Huber E, Farcito S, Gerber L, et al., Development of a new generation of high-resolution anatomical models for medical device evaluation: the Virtual Population 3.0. *Physics in Medicine & Biology*, 2014; 59(18):5287. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-9155/59/18/5287> PMID: 25144615

- Example: The VICTRE trial: an in-silico replica of a clinical trial for evaluating digital breast tomosynthesis as a replacement for full-field digital mammography²⁵⁸
- **Reduce reliance on animal and human testing:** providing an ethical and potentially more cost-effective alternative²⁵⁹.
 - **Example:** *In silico* trials demonstrate higher accuracy than animal testing²⁶⁰, An *in silico* alternative to animal testing²⁶¹

7.3 Barriers to the uptake of in silico trials

Though the *In silico Medicine* community recognises the opportunities^{262,263,264,265} that *in silico* methodologies offer, the uptake in clinical practice is low²⁶⁶. The community acknowledges and actively tries to overcome the challenges associated with integrating these technologies into clinical research and regulatory frameworks. A preliminary analysis of the current state of *in silico* trials at the start of the projects has identified several challenges that may hinder their adoption:

7.3.1 Challenges in the technical development of In silico Trials

Lack of advanced models: A lack of predictive models that are both sophisticated and reliable enough to support the reduction, refinement, or replacement of clinical trials necessary for the approval of new medical products. This includes difficulties in supporting model development and transitioning between black-box and white-box approaches.

Lack of independent validation collections: There is a shortage of publicly available, curated medical datasets specifically designed for developing (e.g., AI-based predictors) and validating *in silico* trial technologies.

²⁵⁸ Sharma D, Graff CG, Badal A, Zeng R, Sawant P, Sengupta A, Dahal E, Badano A. Technical Note: *In silico* imaging tools from the VICTRE clinical trial. *Med Phys*. 2019 Sep;46(9):3924-3928. doi: 10.1002/mp.13674. Epub 2019 Jul 17.

²⁵⁹ Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, et al. Possible Contexts of Use for *In silico* Trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*. 2021;25(10):3977-3982. doi:10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469

²⁶⁰ Passini E, Britton OJ, Lu HR, Rohrbacher J, Hermans AN, Gallacher DJ, Greig RJH, Bueno-Orovio A, Rodriguez B. Human *In Silico* Drug Trials Demonstrate Higher Accuracy than Animal Models in Predicting Clinical Pro-Arrhythmic Cardiotoxicity. *Front Physiol*. 2017 Sep 12;8:668. doi: 10.3389/fphys.2017.00668. PMID: 28955244;

²⁶¹ Borba, Joyce V B et al. "STopTox: An *In Silico* Alternative to Animal Testing for Acute Systemic and Topical Toxicity." *Environmental health perspectives* vol. 130,2 (2022): 27012. doi:10.1289/EHP9341

²⁶² Viceconti, M., Henney, A and Morley-Fletcher, E. (2016) *In silico clinical trials: how computer simulation will transform the biomedical industry*. *International Journal of Clinical Trials*, 3 (2). pp. 37-46. ISSN 2349-3240

²⁶³ Morrison TM, Pathmanathan P, Adwan M and Margerrison E (2018) Advancing Regulatory Science With Computational Modeling for Medical Devices at the FDA's Office of Science and Engineering Laboratories. *Front. Med*. 5:241. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2018.00241

²⁶⁴ For more details on the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) of *in silico* technologies, please see Viceconti, M. (2024). *In silico* Trials: An updated SWOT Analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14221258>

²⁶⁵ Medical Device Innovation Consortium – Landscape Report & Industry Survey on the Use of Computational Modeling & Simulation in Medical Device Development – February 16, 2024- Accessible via: <https://mdic.org/resources/landscape-report-industry-survey-on-the-use-of-computational-modeling-simulation-in-medical-device-development/>

²⁶⁶ Lesage, R., Van Oudheusden, M., Schievano, S., Van Hoyweghen, I., Geris, L., & Capelli, C. (2023). Mapping the use of computational modelling and simulation in clinics: A survey. *Frontiers in Medical Technology*, 5, 1125524–1125524. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmedt.2023.1125524>

Poor Scalability and Efficiency: Many *in silico* models struggle to scale effectively, with limited computational efficiency for handling large-scale population simulations in environments that are user-friendly, secure, and trustworthy.

7.3.2 Challenges in Implementing In silico Trials in Healthcare

Lack of clear regulatory pathways: The lack of established regulatory frameworks creates uncertainty. Addressing this requires extending credibility assessments (such as those outlined in ASME VV-40²⁶⁷) to include models used in pharmaceutical and combination product evaluations, aligning VV-40 with the ISO standardisation framework, gaining "first-in-kind" validation with EMA, and exploring new regulatory pathways for high-risk medical devices and pharmaceutical products. This also involves reducing reliance on human experimentation through *in silico* methods and adopting robust post-marketing surveillance to verify the accuracy of these technologies as they become more widely used.

Lack of clear business models: The lack of commercial exploitation opportunities for any innovation can hinder its survival and prevent it from achieving its objectives. *In silico* trial solutions are no exception and must overcome this significant barrier to fulfil their potential in bringing safe products to patients and improving healthcare. Exploitation is a crucial activity of ISW as it connects the project results to their subsequent market commercialisation, aiming to a broader reach to the pharmaceutical and medical device industry, healthcare professionals and clinical societies, patients and their families, and other stakeholders involved.

Lack of trained workforce: There is a clear gap in training and re-skilling programs to prepare individuals with the technical expertise needed for *in silico* trials across industries, regulatory bodies, hospitals, and related sectors.

Poorly informed stakeholders: Stakeholders, including policymakers, healthcare providers, patients, regulators, payers, CROs, and technology developers, often lack accurate and comprehensive information about *in silico* trials. This highlights the need for rigorous risk-benefit assessment frameworks tailored to the perspectives of diverse stakeholders, ensuring well-informed decision-making and adoption of these technologies.

²⁶⁷ASME VV40 is a standardized framework for assessing the credibility of computational models used in medical applications, ensuring their reliability and suitability for regulatory and clinical decision-making. For more information, visit <https://www.asme.org/getmedia/692ee706-d396-49fd-b62c-d8e3de655a27/21356.pdf>

8 Appendix 2 – Relevant ISW analysis, reports and publications

8.1 List of key reports and resources

Description	Documents, reports, deliverables
Theme 1: Innovation, Technology readiness, Training	
Resources to accelerate adoption of <i>in silico</i> trials	Publication Viceconti, M. (2024, November 4). <i>An in silico world: Resources to accelerate the adoption of in silico trials.</i> Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14035371
Solution Dossier: collection of results from ISW	Internal report Stanic, G., & Caccaro, D. (2024). <i>In silico World Solution Dossier: detailed collection of the results produced within the In silico World project.</i> Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011767
Lecture materials for training and re-training Analysis of training the <i>in silico</i> workforce	Lecture materials Gheysen, L., & Vander Sloten, J. (2024). Training the <i>in silico</i> trials workforce. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14280732 Vander Sloten, J., Gheysen, L., & Stassen, P. (2024). Mini-courses as educational resources for the <i>in silico</i> workforce - Documentation and access. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14525260 K. Vander Linden, G. Van Looy, G. Davico, M. Viceconti and J. Vander Sloten, "A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for <i>In silico</i> Trials", Zenodo, Sep. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8380239 K. Vander Linden, G. Van Looy, G. Davico, M. Viceconti and J. Vander Sloten, "Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on <i>In silico</i> Trials", Zenodo, Dec. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10400657.
Information Package for health care professionals	Public deliverable Rangarajan, J. R., Stanic, G., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Montesarchio, D., & Geris, L. (2024). <i>In silico World D5.6 - Information Package and Lecturing Materials.</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14044934
INFOKIT on stakeholder engagement for modellers	Toolkit: Rangarajan, J. R., et al. The <i>in silico</i> Medicine Info Kit - Vphi. Zenodo, 20 Dec. 2024, doi:10.5281/zenodo.14536119. Multimedia material: VPHi-Animated-Video-Series-Playlist . Abstract: Contin, M., et al. An <i>in silico</i> Medicine Info Kit for Effective Stakeholder Engagement. Zenodo, 2024, doi:10.5281/zenodo.13760091.
Theme 2: Economic opportunity	
Commercial exploitation report	Internal report Carbone, V., Stanculescu, D., Van Rossom, S., & Viceconti, M. (2024). <i>In silico World - Exploitation Public Report.</i> Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14547864

Analysis of strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats	SWOT Analysis Viceconti, M. (2024). <i>In silico</i> Trials: An updated SWOT Analysis. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011927
Theme 3: Policy	
Policy Brief: Accelerating the uptake of <i>in silico</i> trials in healthcare	Public deliverable Geris, L., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Rangarajan, J. R., Biasin, E., Van Hoyweghen, I., & Viceconti, M. (2024). Policy brief: Accelerating the uptake of <i>in silico</i> trials in healthcare. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534366
Report on Desk Review and Delphi Study	Internal report Van Oudheusden, M., Lesage, R., Geris, L., Van Hoyweghen, I. (2023). Internal Survey for ISW General Assembly: A Delphi Approach. https://lirias.kuleuven.be/retrieve/740390 Toolkit: In preparation.
Theme 4: Legal & legislation	
Legal and ethical requirements, with implementation guidelines and recommendations for <i>in silico</i> trial researchers and users	Biasin, E. (2023). <i>In silico</i> World D9.2 In-depth analysis of legal and ethical requirements. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991233 Biasin, E., Corrêa Harcus, A. M., Elhadj, E., & Viceconti, M. (2024). <i>In silico</i> World D9.3 Implementation guidance and guidelines. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11173758 Biasin, E., Corrêa Harcus, A. M., Elhadj, E., & Viceconti, M. (2024). <i>In silico</i> World D9.3 Implementation guidance and guidelines. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11173758
Theme 5: Regulatory	
Regulatory Barriers report	Landscape report Viceconti, M., Pappalardo, F., Curreli, C., Russo, G., & Aldieri, A. (2024). REGULATORY BARRIERS TO THE ADOPTION OF <i>IN SILICO</i> TRIALS (Version v1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948478
Regulatory workshop slides	Meeting presentation Viceconti, M. (2024, March 14). Devices vs. Drugs: statistical inference approaches at the root of an epistemological divide. The regulatory barriers to <i>In silico</i> Trials, Catania, Italy. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14133607
Analysis of training the <i>in silico</i> workforce	Report on lecture materials and pilot training Gheysen, L., & Vander Sloten, J. (2024). Training the <i>in silico</i> trials workforce. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14280732
Perspective report – Present & Future	Meeting presentation Viceconti, M. (2022, October 25). <i>In silico</i> Medicine: Present and Future. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7249043
Theme 6: Ethical and social considerations	
Responsible Research and innovation in practice, as applied to the field of <i>In silico</i> Medicine	Publication Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., & Van Hoyweghen, I. (2024) Brokering responsible research and innovation in <i>in silico</i> medicine, <i>Journal of Responsible Innovation</i> , 11:1, DOI: 10.1080/23299460.2024.2414484